

Selective laser manufacturing of Ti-based alloys and composites: impact of process parameters, application trends, and future prospects

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ABSTRACT

Aviation and automobile industries demand high strength, fatigue resistant, and wear-resistant materials in combination with lightweight, especially for structural applications. On the other hand, biomedical applications demand materials with low modulus and stiffness for optimized implants better matching the modulus of human bone combined with enhanced strength and wear resistance. For all the aforementioned applications in various fields, the fabrication of parts with desired size and shape without the need for joining or welding operations is desired while simultaneously reaching improved mechanical properties and more resistance to environmental attack, which are stringent requirements for almost all the applications. To achieve all these demands, both material developments, as well as modification of process conditions and parameters, are essential. Along these lines, a lot of research work focusses on advanced or even disruptive manufacturing routes and proper alloy development (e.g. Ti, Al, steels, and so on) applying additive manufacturing (AM) techniques for various applications. Among different AM methods, selective laser melting (SLM) is in high demand and preferred for achieving fully dense products in the required dimensions. Titanium alloys designed for AM have replaced a variety of other alloys due to their superior properties such as lightweight or good fatigue and corrosion resistance, achievable through modified microstructures gained by the faster heating and cooling rates realized upon laser printing. Ti alloys with a single (α) or dual ($\alpha+\beta$) microstructure are mostly implemented in the aviation and automobile industries, whereas β alloys with exceptionally low modulus close to that of human bone are intensively studied for bio and dental implants but have not been commercialized yet. The modification of microstructure and properties in Ti-based materials with the addition of suitable reinforcement is also a reliable method. In this article, critical aspects for the optimization of processing parameters affecting the properties of SLM manufactured Ti alloys and titanium matrix composites (TMCs) will be presented, and future prospects of such materials will be critically assessed. This work is expected to be helpful for future studies on Ti alloys and composites with enhanced properties processed by laser manufacturing.

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1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) concerns rapid prototyping manufacturing techniques based on successively stacking up several 2D layers of a material to form 3D objects with great precision. The first patent on AM was filed in 1986 for a

stereolithography technique [1]. In AM techniques, a virtual model prepared by means of a computer-aided design (CAD) software is fed into the AM machine that will 'print' the objects in well-defined dimensions, often precluding additional postprocessing steps [2,3]. Conventional manufacturing methods, on the other hand, require the removal of material (cutting/finishing/drilling, and so on) from bulk/sheet/standard commercial geometries and shapes to get the desired shape, which involves a high input of starting material and considerable material waste during postprocessing. AM enables the

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material to be printed strictly based on the specific design provided by the software and makes it easier to fabricate complex shapes, which may be difficult or even impossible to be manufactured by traditional methods [4,5]. For example, nozzles for fuel injection in space craft's often involve complex structures that are made precisely by AM nowadays, which were previously manufactured by assembling several components [6–9]. The elimination of additional steps involved in assembling several smaller components of a body helps in saving substantial energy, labor and production time. Hence, a multitude of lightweight structures that are applicable in several fields are today fabricated by AM on a commercial scale to reduce the manufacturing costs and save time. In the field of medicine, dental and bone implants, as well as a variety of fixtures such as bone plates, screws, nails, and wires, are now manufactured by additive means, as the technique is capable of creating patient-specific components based on the patient's own medical imaging [10]. Similarly, for other industrial applications, AM of complex-shaped mixing and swirling burners has helped in saving a lot of energy, increased the lifetime of components and reduced the repair charge [11]. Various industrial hardware constituents such as punches, dies and other tools are rapidly manufactured on demand by prototyping.

The classification of AM methods is usually done based on the input energy–powder interaction and the consolidation mechanism. AM methods such as electron beam melting (EBM), selective laser melting (SLM), selective laser sintering (SLS), and laser engineered net shaping (LENS) are the most commonly used techniques to attain high densification, which in turn directly influences the mechanical, corrosion, and thermal properties of a component [12,13]. Fig. 1 gives an overview of the AM techniques used for metals, polymers, and ceramic materials, where the feedstock is powder [14]. Such techniques are classified as powder-bed fusions processes. Over the last few decades, advancements in AM technology have allowed the use of cost-reliable industrial lasers, high-performance software, cost-effective hardware, and advanced feedstock designs [15]. The AM technologies developed at laboratories and research institutions have been also validated and pushed forward in industry in recent years [16]. Prior knowledge about the inherent physical and chemical properties of the starting material (powder) and proper understanding of the specifics for desired applications are essential to achieve defect-free, high performance, and reliable parts by AM.

2. Selective laser melting

Conventional fabrication routes are mostly subtractive processes which remove unwanted layers or edges, fixtures, and so on from a bulk body to obtain the desired shape. SLM is a powder-bed fusion process, which adopts layer-by-layer melting of the powder

using a high-energy laser beam(s) in an inert atmosphere, the melting sequence being in accordance with the CAD [17]. Fig. 2 illustrates the important components of SLM machine. The 3D design is first sliced into several 2D layers of a defined thickness, often in the range of 20–50 μm [18–20]. The powder distribution and melting are then performed on a detachable platform inside the SLM chamber [21–23]. During the process, the powder is fed into the chamber with the help of a hopper feeder mechanism. A recoater blade or roller spreads the powder uniformly over the platform in the form of a thin layer. The laser is exposed on selected regions on the powder layer in conjunction with the design. After exposure, the platform moves down by a distance equal to the predefined layer thickness and the process of powder coating and laser exposure continues until the component is printed completely. The term 'SLM' thus indicates the melting of a selective/partial region on the powder bed. The main components comprising a SLM device are the laser source, the powder feeder, a computer system for instructions and control, an inert atmosphere in the processing chamber and a roller [24]. Fig. 3 shows a schematic representing the step-by-step functioning of an SLM device, adapted from literature [25].

SLM-processed components may achieve full densification with minimal defects subject to the condition that the process parameters are carefully optimized [28–30]. Thus, the parameters need to be properly adjusted for every new material system [31]. One important aspect to be taken care of is that there is no mechanical pressure applied on the powder layer during melting but only gravity, capillary forces and thermal effects contribute mainly in achieving densification upon solidification [32]. The relevant parameters that have to be adjusted can be classified into two groups: powder characteristics and actual process parameters. The powder characteristics encompass material density, melting point, particle size, particle shape, powder flowability, laser reflectivity, thermal conductivity, melt pool viscosity, and so on. Process parameters such as the laser wavelength and laser working mode are usually not varied but are determined by the device itself. The key to successful manufacturing of reliable, defect-free components lies in optimizing the rest of the process parameters such as layer thickness, scanning speed, laser power, and hatch distance/style [32]. The laser energy density ' E ' (defined as the amount of energy supplied to the powder bed) during the process is given by a study by Thijs et al. [9]:

$$E = \frac{P}{t \cdot v \cdot s} \quad (1)$$

where P is the laser power (W), t is the layer thickness (mm), v is the scan speed (mm/s), and s is scan spacing (mm) [33].

Fig. 1. Additive manufacturing techniques for powders [13,14].

Fig. 2. Basic components in a selective laser melting setup [26,27].

The laser power itself has a strong effect on the material characteristics such as density, morphology, and mechanical behavior [34]. The laser power is mostly varied alongside the scan speed to determine the dwell time of the laser beam on the melt surface. The ratio of laser power (P) and scan speed (v) defines the linear energy density (J/m), which is a common and important parameter. From this relation, an increase in either laser power or a decrease in scan speed results in the increase of energy density. To make this clear, Jia and Gu [35] studied the effect of both scan speed and laser power on densification, microstructure and properties of Inconel 718 superalloy. High scan speeds resulted in reduced dwelling time and reduced the melt pool temperature which attributed to poor melt pool dynamics and high porosity [36]. This high scan speed also resulted in coarsened microstructure and high residual thermal stress. On the other hand, reducing the scan speed to a considerable value and increasing the laser power resulted in the more heat generation and prolonged residence of laser beam for attaining optimum viscosity in melt pool and achieved higher density. A finer microstructure can be obtained by optimizing the laser power and scan speed [35,37–39].

During processing, the laser beam moves over the powder bed at a predefined scan speed (v). Higher scan speeds result in shorter fabrication time but may also give rise to incomplete melting and hence defects [28,38,40]. However, in some cases, the laser power may be increased sufficiently to avoid partial melting. The layer thickness is another important parameter that is directly proportional to the average powder particle size. Lack of coherence between the particle size and the powder layer thickness results in either over melting in case of too thin layer thickness or poor bonding between successive layers in case of too thick layers. The scan spacing (s), also called 'hatch space', that is, the separation between parallel laser tracks, is an important factor that determines strong bonding between adjacent laser tracks within a given layer [41–43]. Adjacent hatches are generally made to overlap to avoid porosity and ensure high densification along the layers [39,44,45]. Moreover, the laser beam can be tuned to traverse in several styles along a layer. This defines the 'hatch style' or 'scanning strategy', which is essentially the pattern and length of the laser scanning vectors. The 'manufacturing pattern', which is decided by the scanning strategy and scanning geometry, may be different for different materials or different purposes. The selection of an appropriate manufacturing pattern strongly influences the quality of the fabricated part. The laser scan patterns may involve straight and parallel lines with circular or spiral coverage. The variation in pattern direction can be changed inside a single layer or

between successive layers. Different possible scanning patterns involve unidirectional, bidirectional (zig-zag), interlayer (rotation in direction in different sections of a layer), and interlayer rotational scanning (rotation of scanning direction in consecutive layers), which are shown in Fig. 4 [41,46]. Different rotation angles of scanning are also possible between two layers.

The densification and quality of SLM parts depend on the aforementioned parameters [47,48]. From equation (1), it is clear that the laser energy density can be increased either by increasing the laser power or by decreasing any or all of the parameters including layer thickness, scan speed, and scan spacing. This increased energy density raises the temperature of the powder and thus densification is achieved. Sufficient laser energy density is required to completely melt the layer to attain full densification. A minimum critical energy density is required for maximum densification [8,9,49,50]. For instance, the reported optimized critical laser energy density for attaining fully dense (commercially pure – CP) Ti and Ti-6Al-4V is $\sim 120 J/mm^3$ [51,52] and for Ti-24Nb-4Zr-8Sn, it is around $40 J/mm^3$ [49]. Although the energy density seems to be a sufficient condition to obtain fully dense parts, it has been shown that the laser power is a more important factor and that each parameter defined in equation (1) needs to be optimized individually. This study reported the manufacturing of several parts by systematically varying the parameters in equation (1) in a way that the overall energy density was maintained at a constant value. Despite the same energy density, the parts showed different microstructures and hence varying mechanical properties [53].

Another important parameter that directly affects the total energy input to the material is the shift in focus. Changing the focus means that melting of the powder bed occurs at different heights with respect to a fixed laser position [54]. This results in a different spot size and power density. If R_0 is the minimum radius of the laser spot at the focal point, n is the refractive index of the media through which laser is traveling, z is the distance from the focal plane, Z_r is the Rayleigh distance and λ_0 is the laser wavelength, then the following equation can be used to find the change in spot size with the relative motion of the building plate with respect to the laser [54]:

$$\text{Power density} = \frac{P}{\pi R^2} \quad (2)$$

Here, P is laser power and R is laser spot radius. R can be defined as

Fig. 3. Step-by-step process flow during selective laser melting. Adapted with permission from Taylor & Francis online under the license number 4833061210075 dated 20th May 2020 [25].

$$R(z) = \sqrt[3]{1 + (z/Z_r)^2} \quad (3)$$

Z_r can be expressed as:

$$Z_r = (\pi n R_0^2) / \lambda_0 \quad (4)$$

The divergence of the Gaussian distribution directly affects the laser energy density via the laser spot size [34]. The aforementioned equations (2)–(4) explain the change in power density with the change in focal length. The change in focal length either in positive or negative direction from the plane will reduce the power density drastically as compared with other parameters. This phenomenon has already been observed and reported in laser welding [55]. A variation in microstructure and porosity may be observed due to the change in power density, resulting from the focal shift. Hitherto, there are only a limited number of available reports that have addressed the effect of focal plane shift and power density on the resulting properties. For example, Helmer et al. [56] reported the effect of focal shift on the microstructure for EBM. A possible similarity for SLM was suggested by McLouth et al. [54] and Bean et al. [34], who studied the effect of the laser focus shift on the microstructure and density, respectively, for Inconel 718. The effect of focal shift on the pool morphology is depicted in Fig. 5, where ‘0’ focal shift results in a deep and narrow melt pool, whereas +3 and –3 shifts result in a shallow and wide pool, respectively. The minimum porosity was reported in case of –3 laser focus shift [54].

Yadroitsev et al. [57] and Wang et al. [58] investigated the effect of scan speed and laser power on the linear energy density. Further, Campanelli et al. [59] have emphasized the significance of surface energy density (E_d) by accounting for the laser spot diameter (d_{spot}) and the laser power (P) as expressed in the following equations (5) and (6):

$$E_d = P / (v \cdot d_{spot}) \left[\frac{J}{mm^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

Ciurana et al. [60] and Gunenthiram et al. [61] studied the influence of the volumetric energy density on densification by

considering scan speed (v), laser diameter (d_{spot}), and layer thickness (t) considering the relation:

$$VED = P / (v \cdot d_{spot} \cdot t) \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] \quad (6)$$

By using the normalized enthalpy, predictions of the melt pool depth and the threshold for keyhole formation have been provided by King et al. [62] by considering material properties such as absorptivity (A), thermal diffusivity (D), and enthalpy at melting (h_s). The relation uses equations (7) and (8):

$$\frac{\Delta H}{h_s} = \frac{A \cdot P}{\pi \cdot h_s \cdot \sqrt{D \cdot v \cdot d_{spot}^3}} \quad (7)$$

$$h_s = c_p \cdot \rho \cdot (T_m - T_0) \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] \quad (8)$$

where, c_p is the specific heat capacity, ρ is the density, T_m is the melting temperature and T_0 is the initial temperature before melting [63].

The relation between the laser spot size and power on the densification and dimensional accuracy of SLM parts is highly sensitive. The use of an optimum beam diameter and laser power combination is very important so that defects and possible material evaporation can be avoided. Therefore, current commercial SLM machines tend to combine a small beam diameter (~60 μm) with laser powers up to 400 W, or another combination of larger beam diameter (~100 to 500 μm) coupled with higher laser power up to 1 kW [64]. Using a small beam diameter with very high laser power can cause material evaporation and keyholes due to very concentrated energy and overheating at a small spot. Therefore, increasing the laser spot size allows using high power lasers without overheating, but this may compromise with the precision and surface roughness of the parts. To resolve this issue, a new approach, known as ‘hull-core’ strategy has been suggested [65]. This strategy involves a high productivity parameter set for the core and a high precision parameter set for the outer region, which results in a

Fig. 4. Different possible scanning patterns (a) unidirectional (b) bidirectional (zigzag) (c) interlayer (d) interlayer rotation, during SLM processing. Adapted with permission from Taylor & Francis online under the license number 4844031142019 dated 8th June 2020 [46]. SLM, selective laser melting;

combination of properties such as high build rate, high geometrical precision, and low surface roughness. The core parameter set involves larger spot size, larger hatch spacing, and higher layer thickness, which provides a larger melt pool inside the part. Schleifenbaum et al. [66] and Bremen et al. [67] used two different lasers to obtain this combination of properties. A Gaussian beam with a diameter of 80–200 μm was used for hull scanning and a top-hat beam with a diameter around 700–1100 μm was used for the core. To ease the complication of using multiple laser setups, a shift of the focal plane can also be an alternative to increase the laser spot size or defocusing the beam [64].

3. Development of laser-based Ti alloys

Among all the available metals, Ti is 9th most common element in the earth crust but an expensive metal due to the high cost of reduction and refining its ores [13]. Ti and its alloys are in extreme demand in various fields including automobile, aerospace, defense, chemical industries, and medical applications due to their exceptional combination of properties. The excellent corrosion resistance of Ti makes it reliable for use in chemical processing plants, the high specific strength is advantageous for applications in aerospace industries, whereas low modulus Ti alloys have made a

Fig. 5. Variation in melt pool morphology with respect to laser focal shift: (a) +3, (b) 0, and (c) -3 [54]. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833070760462 dated 20th May 2020 [54].

breakthrough as advanced implant materials in the biomedical area in recent time. A number of few important alloys has been specifically used in these different fields, as listed in Table 1, and some of them are slowly replaced nowadays by Ti and Ti alloys owing to their versatile properties.

Table 2 lists different commercial Ti alloys used in aviation industry along with the automobile and biomedical sectors. The mechanical properties of technically pure Ti are considered by a good combination of strength and ductility [74]. As an example, the tensile and yield strength of pure Ti is 540 MPa and 410 MPa, respectively, with an elongation of $\geq 20\%$. But these properties depend upon the impurity content, especially due to oxygen, nitrogen, hydrogen, carbon, iron, and silicon [74]. They increase the strength but sharply degrade the plasticity and mostly gaseous play the major role in this. In the presence of $>0.01\%$ H, 0.24% N, or $>0.5\%$ O, titanium completely loses the ability to process through plastic deformation and brittleness occur, which limits its applications [74]. Hydrogen is less soluble in α phase and forms hydride, which reduces the impact strength results in hydrogen embrittlement [75]. Therefore, the content of impurity, especially the gaseous impurities are advised to keep strictly limited. The phases formed at different temperature schedules during manufacturing decide the final properties of the fabricated part and thus its applicability.

Ti has two polymorphic forms [78]. Below 882.5°C , it exists as α -Ti phase with hexagonal close-packed (hcp) structure and above this temperature, it transforms to the β -Ti phase with body-centered cubic (bcc) structure. Different alloying elements, as well

as processing parameters such as cooling rates have a strong impact on the stability and properties of the different Ti phases [79,80]. Despite of having a combination of tremendous properties such as low weight, high strength, and good corrosion resistance, the use of Ti and Ti alloys is limited to applications where its expense can be justified. Traditionally, Ti alloys are manufactured by casting, forging or powder metallurgy processes, often followed by post-processing steps such as machining, heat treatments or surface treatments to achieve the desired properties [81–84]. However, the low thermal conductivity of Ti and its high chemical reactivity during machining require the use of excess energy making the final components rather expensive. In this context, SLM is a better suited manufacturing method for Ti-based materials because the final part can be obtained in desired shape and size without the need of cutting/joining/machining, thus saving a lot of energy and time [81,85–88]. Several efforts have been undertaken to optimize the process parameters to attain the required properties in Ti alloys. These efforts were based on the correlation of the physical characteristics such as roughness, porosity, microstructure, and so on to the mechanical, biological, or corrosion properties of the parts prepared using different process parameters in different studies. For example, Benedetti et al. [89] reported high porosity and surface roughness together with poor fatigue properties for a Ti-6Al-4V alloy prepared by SLS. Recently, the work on Ti and its alloys processed by SLM has become the focus of international research due to the increased demand in biomedical applications. Gu et al. [52] have optimized the processing parameters to attain 99.5%

Table 1
Different alloys and their applications [68–73].

Alloy specification		Applications						
		Aerospace	Medical	Oil, gas and energy industries	Automobile	Marine	High temperature applications	Tools and molds
Alloys	Al	✓			✓			
	Stainless steel	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Ti	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
	Co-Cr	✓	✓					
	Ni superalloys	✓				✓	✓	
	Noble metals		✓					

Table 2
Application of different Ti alloys in several sectors [74,76,77].

Alloy	Applications
Aircrafts	
Ti-Al-2.5 (Gr-9)	Hydraulic high pressure lines, replacing stainless steel pipe thus reducing a total 40% weight. It is used for the production of cell structures.
Ti-5Al-2.5Sn (Gr-6)	Used in tempered state in cryogenic technique due to good strength and ductility at low temperatures. Used in the turbo-pumps high pressure space shuttles.
Ti-8Al-1Mo-1V	Used for the blades of military engines
Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-Mo (+ Si)	Used mainly in the parts of gas turbines, including disks and rotors at temperatures up to around 540°C , in the high pressure compressors.
Ti-6Al-4V	Used in gas turbine engines for both static and rotating components, including all parts of the aircrafts – fuselage, nacelles, landing gear, wing and tail surfaces as well as the structure for the support of floor.
Ti-6Al-2Sn-2Zr-2Mo-2Cr + Si	Used for F-22 program for Lockheed/Boeing
Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-6Mo	Used above 315°C temperature, especially for military engines such as F-100 and F-119, with yield strength of 1035 MPa.
Ti-5Al-2Sn-2Zr-4Mo-4Cr	Used at temperature $<400^\circ\text{C}$ for fans and compressor disks.
Ti-13Al-11Cr-3Al	Widely used in aircraft SR-71 for the wings, body, frames, partitions and ribs.
Ti-10V-2Fe-3Al	Almost the whole main landing gear of Boeing 77 is produced from this alloy, leading to a weight reduction of around 270 Kg per airplane.
Automobile sector	
Ti-6Al-4V	Spring suspension, bumper, exhaust valves, connecting rods
Gr-4, Ti6Al4V	Body, Fuselage
Gr-2, Ti-6Al-4V, Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo-0.1Si	Exhaust valves
Gr-2	Exhaust system
Biomedical sector	
Commercially pure titanium (Gr-1, 2, 3, 4), Ti-6Al-4V, Ti-6Al-7Nb, Ti-5Al-1.5B, Ti-16Nb-13Ta-4Mo, Ti-12Mo-6Zr-2Fe, Ti-15Mo-5Zr-3Al, Ti-13Nb-13Zr, Ti-27Nb-7Fe-xCr, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4Mo, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-6Sn, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Sn, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.5Zr, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-2Sn, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-7.1Zr, Ti-48Nb-2Nb-0.7Cr-0.3Si, and so on	

relative density in CP-Ti. The correlation between porosity, microstructure and mechanical properties has also been analyzed with respect to the processing parameters. Wysocki et al. [90], Li et al. [91] and Attar et al. [50] have reported increased compressive strength, hardness and tensile strength for SLM produced CP-Ti compared with conventionally prepared cast material. The production of Ti-6Al-4V alloy samples using SLS followed by hot pressing has been reported by Das et al. [92]. In this study, the properties and microstructure were analogous to the conventionally prepared Ti-6Al-4V alloys. The suitability of Ti alloys for applications is mostly based on the properties of the material and, therefore, Ti alloys are predominantly utilized in aviation and biomedical sectors (where costs are not the limiting factor) due to their favorable mechanical properties. The following sections address the progress made in the AM of different types of Ti alloys used in these two areas:

3.1. α , β and $(\alpha+\beta)$ -Ti alloys used in aviation industry

Ti alloys are about half as heavy as steel or Ni-based super alloys and provide an outstanding strength-to-weight ratio. The majority of the components used in aerospace systems are composed of Ti alloys. Commercially viable parts include airframes, gas turbine engines, fuselages of helicopters and spacecrafts, and so on.

Ti alloys are an ideal replacement for steel and aluminum in fuselages due to their high specific strength and capability to inhibit fatigue crack growth [93–95]. They are used as thin, narrow rings around the Al aircraft fuselage similar to a ‘belly band’ to retard catastrophic fatigue cracks [96]. One of the first applications of Ti alloys in the aerospace industry involved the use of $(\alpha+\beta)$ -type Ti3Al2.5V for hydraulic tubes [97]. Ti alloys are also used for parts requiring high corrosion resistance including aircraft floors, toilets and on-board kitchens, and piping systems used in deicing equipment due to stringent thermal stability requirements [93]. Along with commercial applications, Ti alloys are extensively used for fighter jet bodies due to ‘aero-kinetic heating’ that cannot be borne by Al alloys [96]. For example, Ti-6Al-2Zr-2Sn-2Mo-2Cr-0.25Si is used for airframes of US F-22 jets and Joint-strike fighter projects [96]. β Ti alloys such as Ti-3Al-8V-6Cr-4Mo-4Zr (β -C) and Ti-15V-3Cr-3Sn-3Al are preferred for making springs for multiple aircraft actuation systems [98].

The aircraft industry is expected to commission 28,000 new commercial aircrafts and around 10,000 replacements during 2012–2031 on a global scale [99]. Along with this, a demand for 5000 jets with a total market value of up to 200 billion US \$ is planned in the next few years. The aviation program Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in the EU 2020 and Flight path 2050 target a reduction of fuel consumption and harmful gas emission in the aerospace sector, which demands an upgrade in both technology and material design [99]. The use of lightweight structures realized via economic processing methods is

an effective approach to reduce fuel consumption, as well as harmful greenhouse gas emissions. SLM is one of the advanced manufacturing methods, which is significantly more efficient than any other conventional fabrication route to achieve the aforementioned goals. In this context, for example, Embraer and Fraunhofer IPK collaborate for investigating the mechanical behavior of SLM fabricated Ti parts for structural aerospace applications [99]. Similarly, Boeing has fabricated 200 different parts for 10 aircraft platforms using AM, and it has produced about 20,000 parts for military and commercial aircrafts including 32 different components for its 787 Dreamliner planes [94]. General electric, the world’s largest jet engine supplier, produces fuel nozzles for thousands of jet engines that are claimed to have 25% less weight and 5 times more durability than state-of-the-art parts, which were previously made by welding of 20 different parts [100]. SLM has been reported as one of the most reliable AM methods by Rafi et al. [101], able to produce such lightweight parts for aerospace applications with reduced CO₂ emission. Tomlin and Myer [102] have shown the practical viability of EBM for creating Airbus A320 nacelle hinge bracket components. Formerly, they were made from near-net shape sand cast HC 101 steel. The use of Ti in place of steel results in 64% weight reduction [102].

α -Ti alloys are reported to have better creep resistance and good weldability compared with $(\alpha+\beta)$ and β -alloys [103,104]. These alloys have hexagonal close-packed crystal structure and are preferably used for cryogenic applications where the content of interstitial elements should be extremely low [105]. They also find applications in gas turbine engines, petrochemical industries and aeronautics [106]. Ti-5Al-2.5Sn, an α -Ti alloy developed in the 1950s, has shown highly reliable performance and is used since many years [107]. However, processing of this alloy is technologically challenging. Casting and hot working impose adverse impact on the production efficiency and product quality due to the high specific yield stress and low thermal conductivity of this alloy [108,109]. Wei et al. [109] reported a preliminary study on single track and bulk processing of Ti-5Al-2.5Sn alloy by SLM. As-printed samples were found to show better fatigue performance than forged samples at high peak cyclic stresses beyond 700 MPa [109]. The authors have also reported statistically identical isotropic tensile behavior for the SLMed Ti-5Al-2.5Sn alloy in both horizontal and vertical directions [110]. Different laser parameters were used for optimizing the densification and resulting mechanical properties. An optimum energy density of 167 J/mm³ was sufficient for to get maximum densification and minimum porosity in specimens. The amount of surface porosity for Ti-5Al-2.5Sn samples fabricated at different laser energy inputs: (a, b) 208 J/mm³; (c, d) 167 J/mm³; (e, f) 51 J/mm³ can be seen in the optical micrographs as shown in Fig. 6.

Lower energy density, that is, 51 J/mm³ caused the lack of fusion and resulted in the poor densification, whereas the higher energy

Fig. 6. Porosity distribution of Ti-5Al-2.5Sn samples, fabricated at different laser energy inputs: (a) 208 J/mm³; (b) 167 J/mm³; (c) 51 J/mm³. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844031482731 dated 8th June 2020 [110].

Fig. 7. Optical microscopy (OM) and SEM images of the Ti-5Al-2.5Sn samples fabricated at different laser energy inputs: (a, b) 208 J/mm³; (c, d) 167 J/mm³; (e, f) 51 J/mm³. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844031482731 dated 8th June 2020 [110].

density (208 J/mm³) above the optimized value resulted in a large number of spherical pores in fabricated samples. The variation in energy input has also shown a significant influence on microstructure and phase formation. The microstructure features showed a prior-β (bcc) matrix, containing mainly martensitic α' (hcp) needles and a few strip-like α-grain boundaries surrounding the prior-β region up to 167 J/mm³ input. Relatively higher energy density (208 J/mm³) resulted in a duplex microstructure α' needles and α grains within the prior-β matrix [110]. The change in microstructural behavior of Ti-5Al-2.5Sn samples at different energy density input, that is, 208 J/mm³, 167 J/mm³, and 51 J/mm³ is shown with the help of optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images in Fig. 7. The ultimate tensile strength was also

maximum for the samples prepared at optimum energy density (i.e. 167 J/mm³), accrediting to the higher densification and martensitic rich microstructure [109].

Ti-6Al-4V alone covers about 50% of the total Ti alloys production. This alloy has a (α+β) dual-phase structure with a highly desirable combination of properties such as low density, high strength, and high temperature resistance, as well as excellent corrosion resistance [111]. These properties have made this alloy the most commonly explored alloy for both aviation and biomedical applications [112]. Ti-6Al-4V is commonly used in gas turbines due to its high-temperature resistance [113]. Its properties strongly depend on the grain size and the arrangement of α and β phases, both of which are governed by the cooling rate applied during

fabrication. Rapid cooling in case of SLM results in grain refinement and microstructure modification that better suits the applications addressed earlier [18,44,99,114,115].

AM Ti-6Al-4V is used as a commercial Ti alloy containing fine acicular α' martensite as dominant phase together with a fraction of β grains [9,116]. The presence of ($\alpha'+\beta$) in place of ($\alpha+\beta$) phases in the microstructure is attributed to the fast cooling during SLM [116]. The transition in microstructure can be observed in Fig. 8 [116,117]. The reported microhardness of fully densified SLM Ti-6Al-4V parts is about 409 Hv (4.011 GPa), which is higher than for parts prepared by superplastic forming (346 Hv [3.393 GPa]) [118]. These higher values are attributed to the presence of the martensite phase in the microstructure. Owing to these promising properties, significant consideration has been given to the fabrication of Ti-6Al-4V by SLM to replace CP-Ti parts [32].

An anisotropic mechanical behavior of a 3D Ti-6Al-4V cruciform component produced by directed energy deposition, a manufacturing method that is similar to SLM, has been reported by Carroll et al. [119]. The average tensile strength was 1060 MPa in both directions, whereas the elongation in longitudinal and transverse directions was found to be 11 and 14%, respectively [119]. The authors claimed to achieve similar strength but improved ductility in direct prepared Ti-6Al-4V samples [119] as compared to the earlier reported values for samples those were heat treated after manufacturing [92,120]. This improved ductility was attributed to the absence of defects (pores) which generally occur due to the lack of fusion. The increase in ultimate and yield strength without losing the ductility in component was achieved by the increase in oxygen level up to 0.0125 wt% and reducing the α -lath width by controlling temperature profile at different building heights [119].

Several other studies were performed on Ti-Al-V alloys produced by SLM [121–123], motivated by the fact that such alloys exhibit excellent high temperature mechanical properties comparable to Ni-based super alloys [121]. TiAl intermetallic (IMC)-based alloys have found to be appropriate for use in aerospace applications due to higher creep strength and oxidation resistance [124], but these IMCs compounds have low fracture toughness and low ductility which limits their applications [125–127]. Gao et al. [121] have used SLM of the Ti-40Al-9V-0.5Y alloy. SLM can be a revolutionary method to manufacture γ -TiAl-based alloys, but these alloys are prone to cracks when heated and cooled multiple times

[121]. Therefore, the effect of process parameters on the crack sensitivity of such alloys was studied extensively [121]. For example, Thomas et al. [128] used preheating of the substrate for AM printing such alloys, attempting to reduce the crack susceptibility. Other reports [125,129,130] have suggested further parameter optimization and increased energy input for these alloys. However, the studies concerning crack formation, heat transfer, and possible remedy were not systematic, as reported by Gao et al. [121]. For crack inhibition, inclusion of vanadium and yttrium that should trigger the development of a fine equiaxed microstructure and favorable mechanical behavior, has been suggested [121]. In addition, a lower cooling rate has been suggested to be advantageous for obtaining finer microstructures and a lower fraction of brittle phases, resulting in crack-free samples [121].

Another Ti-Al alloy, that is, TA15 with Ti-6Al-2Zr-1Mo-1V stoichiometry, possesses good thermal strength, weldability and shows better ductility than ($\alpha+\beta$)-Ti alloys [131]. In comparison with Ti-6Al-4V, this alloy shows a higher fatigue limit, higher strength at elevated temperature, as well as improved fracture toughness, welding performance and corrosion resistance [132,133]. Therefore, it has been used for load-bearing and high temperature resistant (<500 °C) components in missiles, satellites, and aircrafts for longer time [133]. SLM processing of the TA15 alloy and its microstructure-property correlation have been reported by Wu et al. [123]. A similar alloy, Ti-6.5Al-2Zr-Mo-V, which is a near-alpha alloy with high Al content, is also considered for aviation applications for high service temperatures (<500 °C). Wang et al. [134] have performed fatigue tests at three stress levels for direct energy deposited alloy specimens. The aim of this study was to study the crack initiation mechanism and its effect on the fatigue life. Crack formation was found to be induced by internal pores. In addition, Al segregation was found to occur at the pore surface, making it brittle and crack-sensitive, which results in fatigue failure. The authors have established a linear relationship between pore diameter and fatigue life [134]. Jiang et al. [122], recently performed heat treatment studies on the TA 15 alloy for microstructure modification to make applications of this alloy possible. Fine martensite structures along with dislocations and twins were reported for the SLM fabricated samples, showing high strength and high hardness but low plasticity [122]. Heat-treated samples showed a fine basket weave ($\alpha+\beta$)-phase structure with nanoscale β precipitates in the grains. The heat-treated samples were found to have significantly improved mechanical properties compared with as-built or conventionally fabricated samples. Both the as-SLMed and heat-treated samples exhibit a weak texture and anisotropic mechanical properties [122]. Another study focused on a ($\alpha+\beta$)-Ti-6.5Al-3.5Mo-1.5Zr-0.3Si alloy, also named TC11, fabricated through a similar method namely, laser melting deposition [135]. For these samples, columnar grains and a strong β <001> texture parallel to the deposition direction were reported. Increased strength along with ductility without anisotropy was reported for ($\alpha+\beta$) annealing [135]. Similarly, a Ti45Al2Cr5Nb alloy manufactured by SLM also showed superior hardness and microstructure compared with the cast alloy [136,137].

As has been reported [138,139], 60% of all structures fail because of fatigue damage during practical applications. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the fatigue behavior. Some studies, reporting the effect of microstructure and defects on the fatigue behavior of additively manufactured Ti-based alloys are discussed here. Zhan [139] reported the fabrication of a novel TA2-TA15 Ti alloy by laser melting diffusion. Combined experimental and numerical investigations on the alloys TA2, TA15 and LMD TA2-TA15 revealed LMD TA2-TA15 as an ideal choice when considering the manufacturing speed, whereas TA15 was found to have maximum strength and stiffness. The mechanical properties such as yield

Fig. 8. Ti-6Al-4V microstructure of samples manufactured by SLM. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833070937453 dated 20th May 2020 [116]. SLM, selective laser melting.

stress, Young's modulus, fatigue limit and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of LMD TA2-TA15 are intermediate to that of TA2 and TA15 alloys and thus have been recommended for practical applications.

Nb is a β phase stabilizer used for alloys that are more corrosion resistant than Ti-Al-V [140,141]. Along this line, investigations have been conducted on SLMed alloys with different Nb contents [141], including studies on $(\alpha+\beta)$ -Ti-6Al-7Nb [142–144]. This alloy has better corrosion resistance and higher mechanical properties than Ti-6Al-4V [145]. Although these SLM-fabricated alloys have a microstructure comprised both α' martensitic plates and β grains, they show higher hardness and tensile strength, which is ascribed to different impacting features such as residual stress, amount of pores and layer arrangement with respect to the tension direction. The correlation between microstructure and properties like fatigue, hardness and strength has been deeply investigated [144,146,147]. Higher tensile and ultimate strengths, but poor ductility was observed for SLMed alloy variants in contrast to specimens prepared by EBM or casting [145].

A comparative study on Ti-5Al, Ti-6Al-7Nb and Ti-22Al-25Nb alloys obtained by SLM was carried out by Polozov et al. [146] using elemental powders, which showed compositional inhomogeneity and poor mechanical behavior. Later, Zhou et al. [148] investigated the phase formation and strengthening behavior of as-fabricated Ti-22Al-25Nb IMCs using prealloyed powder. A detailed study on the effect of process parameters on grain size, tensile behavior, and complex shape formation of the Ti-22Al-25Nb alloy has been subsequently performed by the same group [149]. They reported a dual phase microstructure consisting of disordered β and α phases in the samples. An optimized hatch density was found to improve the tensile properties by increasing the dislocation density, along with reduced grain size and high relative density.

Ti55511, Ti5553 or Ti1023 and similar alloys are near-beta alloys that are used extensively in aerospace applications [150]. The Ti55511 alloy, also known as TC18 and VT22, is mainly used for load-bearing structural components such as landing gears and flap tracks in aircrafts [151]. This alloy has a mixed bcc and hcp phase microstructure [151]. Ti-50%Ta, a promising biomedical alloy, was fabricated by SLM and a low elastic modulus was obtained, outperforming Ti-6Al-4V [152]. SLM of the near- β Ti5553 (Ti-5Al-5V-5Mo-3Cr) alloy has been investigated for structural and aerospace applications [153]. This alloy shows superior tensile properties compared with parts made from traditional alloys [154,155]. Schwab et al. [153] have studied Ti5553 using SLM. This alloy has good ductility and high strength, thus providing improved high cycle fatigue behavior. A fully dense and pure β -phase microstructure has been reported in their investigation. The reported UTS reached 800 MPa with a maximum elongation of ~14%. This study suggests a possible improvement in ductility with suitable parameter optimization for this alloy. They also suggested a post-processing treatment for increasing the strength for specific industrial applications [153]. Zopp et al. [156] obtained significantly higher tensile strength for the metastable Ti5553 alloy in comparison with Ti-6Al-4V for aerospace applications. A tensile strength of 1400 MPa and a yield strength of 1250 MPa were achieved. The aim of their study was to manipulate the initial particle size and size distribution to achieve higher strength by optimizing the laser parameters, obtaining a minimum densification of above 99.9% [156].

Extensive studies have been carried out worldwide to optimize and standardize the processing conditions of industrially important alloys to improve their operational efficiency. In case of laser AM, Qin et al. [157] have combined SLM and Laser direct metal manufacturing (LDM) methods for hybrid manufacturing of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy. As per the literature [158], LDM-manufactured Ti-6Al-

4V has an $(\alpha+\beta)$ microstructure, whereas SLM-produced Ti-6Al-4V contains an acicular martensite phase [159,160]. However, both methods result in a combination of high strength and low ductility, as is also evident from other studies [160–162], which is not ideal for applications. Therefore, Qin et al.'s work [157] is encouraging as it suggests that combining both AM methods allows us to attain an optimum combination of strength and ductility, at least for the Ti-6Al-4V alloy. Larger columnar grains were found in the LDM zone, whereas finer grains comprised the SLM zone. The microstructures obtained for Ti-6Al-4V alloy in different regions (a) Complete SLM-LDM, (b, c) cross-section of SLM zone, (d) heat affected zone (HAZ) zone and (e) LDM zone are shown in Fig. 9. The HAZ zone exhibited excessive transition from α' to α laths. In addition, several cyclic thermal treatments were performed on the as-prepared hybrid alloy to homogenize the microstructure. Among all the three LDM, HAZ, and SLM zones, the maximum hardness was found in the SLM zone, which was equivalent to 410 ± 10 Hv_{0.2} (4.021 ± 0.09 GPa) after a 6-fold cyclic thermal treatment. The strength was not much affected after the treatment but the plasticity of the LDM zone improved and the tensile behavior of the composite was found to be similar to that of the LDM samples [157].

Besides hybrid manufacturing, also postprocessing has been found an effective route to decrease defects and increase the overall performance. In this area, Lu et al. [163] studied ways for structure control, improvement of mechanical properties and reduced cracking of Ti-6Al-4V by using surface treatment methods. They suggested laser shot-peening as an effective treatment to refine the coarse-grained microstructure and induce compressive residual stresses. A high density of dislocations and mechanical twins in the α' martensite grains were reported to be responsible for improved mechanical behavior. This refinement resulted in increased hardness and a combination of high UTS and ductility [163].

Carlton et al. [164] reported on the effect of heat treatment up to the β -transus temperature for SLM prepared Ti5553 alloys with the aim of increasing their strength for aerospace applications. A short isothermal heat treatment of SLMed Ti5553 alloy is reported to show a wide range of strength and ductility [164]. After a correlative study between X-ray diffraction (XRD) and SEM of heat treated (300 to 800 °C) samples, presence of major β phase with possible ω is reported until 300 °C, whereas it was observed that both α and β phases are present for 500–800 °C heat treated samples. In between 400 and 500 °C, ductility was found to fell from 17 to <2% which was assumed due to the presence of fine α precipitates. The increase in ductility along with a slight decreased yield and ultimate strength was observed at higher heat treating temperatures (700–800 °C) due to the presence of α/β phase [164].

Ti55531 (Ti-5Al-5Mo-5V-3Cr-1Zr) is a high tensile strength, fatigue resistant and corrosion resistant near- β Ti alloy [165]. Deng et al. [166] reported laser metal deposition of Ti-55531 and the results of subsequent heat treatments. As-deposited samples were found to contain β phase with heterogeneously distributed α phase due to a ubiquitous temperature gradient during fabrication. This results in anisotropic tensile properties, which deemed the samples unsuitable for aeronautical applications. Thus, the authors used two different heat treatments (i.e. β solution treatment subsequent aging [β -STA] and triplex annealing [α/β -STA]) on the deposited samples for minimizing anisotropy and making the microstructure more uniform. The increased ultimate tensile strength (>1350 MPa) with low ductility (<6.5%) results from a transformed β microstructure in β -STA condition. The bimodal structure in specimens subjected to α/β -STA treatment was found to exhibit a good combination of UTS (>1200 MPa) and ductility (>8%) [166].

Fig. 9. Microstructures of as-built Ti-6Al-4V alloy: (a) the whole LDM-SLM hybrid manufacturing components, (b) and (c) cross-section of SLM zone, (d) HAZ zone, (e) LDM zone. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844040353877 dated 8th June 2020 [157]. SLM, selective laser melting; HAZ, heat affected zone.

3.2. Proposed β Ti alloys for orthopedic and dental implants

The overwhelming demand for bioimplants can be perceived from the statistics forecast that the number of hip and knee revise surgeries is expected to increase by approximately 137% and 602%, respectively, from 2005 to 2030 [167,168]. Therefore, the development of high-performance, safe and cost-effective biomaterials and implants are of utmost importance. Ti alloys possess a combination of attractive properties to be used for bio applications including excellent biocompatibility, negligible toxicity, high corrosion resistance, and excellent specific strength [46,169]. Ti alloys have a lower Young's modulus than all other available and investigated biomedical alloys, as can be seen from Table 3, given in the following.

In biomedical applications, especially for implant and joint replacements, the implant should have a Young's modulus matching that of human bone (10–30 GPa) as closely as possible [81]. Steels such as SS316 have a Young's modulus of about 210 GPa and Co-Cr alloys show a Young's modulus of around 240 GPa – values that are much higher than that of human bone. This large difference in Young's modulus between implant and bone results in bone resorption, also known as 'stress shielding effect' [171]. This can cause implant loosening and may also require revision surgery [170]. Motivated by these causes, continuous and extensive studies on manufacturing and design of different kinds of titanium alloys have been performed over the years to develop materials with suitable modulus matching with human bone [4,172]. Among metallic alloys, Ti alloys possess Young's moduli in the range of 55–110 GPa and some of these alloys are completely nontoxic [173].

Table 3
Young's modulus of several alloys used in biomedical applications [13,170].

Alloy	Young's modulus (GPa)
Cortical bone	7–30
ANSI 316L stainless steel	210
Cast CoCr	240
CP-Ti	100
Ti-6Al-4V	112
Ti6Al7Nb	110
β -Ti alloys	40–80

These moduli are in the desirable range in comparison with other alloys for implant applications but still higher than that of natural bone [13]. The weight of our body and also the stresses exerted by muscles keep the skeleton of our body under continuous loading conditions [13]. The details of loading at different sites of the skeleton may vary and thus the density and mechanical strength of different bones vary in the human body [174]. Specific bones such as femur and mandible bone are denser because of high loading conditions, whereas some other bones such as finger bones have lower densities due to lower loading conditions. The activity of different body parts can also cause a variation in bone density. From Wolff's law [175], the effect of stress shielding can be same as the use of stiffer implant material. Material with high stiffness bears the majority of load, which results in a drop in the load to the surrounding bone.

Although ($\alpha+\beta$) titanium alloys are conventionally considered as ultimate choice for replacing 316L stainless steel and cobalt-chromium alloys for biomedical applications, FDA-approved Ti-6Al-4V implants fail to match the modulus of bone, thus promoting the formation of fibrous tissue thereby limiting osteointegration [176]. The alloy was further found to release Al and V ions that may cause long-term neurotoxic effects, osteomalacia, and Alzheimer's disease [168,177,178]. To resolve the problem of stress shielding, a variety of β -alloys have been developed with low modulus, almost half of that of conventional Ti [8,156,179]. These β -Ti alloys have an even lower elastic modulus than the ($\alpha+\beta$)-Ti alloys [150,153]. Low modulus β -type titanium alloys were introduced in the early 1980s [180] for biomedical applications, as they comprise non-toxic elements and account for a larger amount of β -stabilizers (Mo, V, W, Nb, Ta, Fe, Cr, Cu, Ni, Co, Mn, and Si) with contents typically ranging between 10 and 20 wt% [181,182]. β -Ti alloys are highly corrosion resistant, and their low modulus is comparable with that of human bone, thereby resulting in a curtailed stress shielding effect [13,170]. These attributes make β -Ti alloys promising candidates for use in orthodontic wires, dental roots and bridges, bone plates, femoral stem, total hip replacements, knee arthroplasties, and spinal fixation [183]. The β -phase also contributes to favorable heat treatability, forming capabilities, and room temperature strength [118].

AM of β -Ti alloys fulfills the need of reducing the modulus and weight of an implant by facilitating the freedom to make porous

structures. This also helps in improving cell in-growth and can be used for bone grafting and joint surgeries [176]. For the fabrication of Ti alloys, different conventional processing routes are used, mainly comprising powder metallurgy (P/M) techniques, casting, foaming, forging and space holder technology, which are followed by machining to give the desired shape and dimensional accuracy [184–189]. After fabrication, the properties of these alloys are enhanced by using postfabrication techniques such as heat treatments or surface treatments [150]. These conventional methods consume excess time and energy, which makes the process expensive for commercial production. For the last few years, AM has been widely used owing to its highly efficient approach of manufacturing. AM is gaining momentum in the medical area due to the freedom of design in developing patient-specific implants at a faster pace, with complex geometries [81]. In addition, the requirement for postprocessing is reduced or even minimum, thus helping to produce high quality parts in less time and at low cost with minimum material loss. Ti alloys, in addition to being expensive, are difficult to machine by conventional methods and, hence, SLM is the ideal processing technique to obtain complex geometries with minimal waste [190–193]. The only limitation in manufacturing β -Ti alloys additively is the availability of feedstock powders and the high cost of powder manufacturing [194,195]. For the ease of understanding, different β -Ti alloys have been categorized into binary, ternary, quaternary, and other alloys.

3.2.1. Binary β -alloys

β -type Ti-X (X = V, Cr, Nb, Mo, Ta) alloys possess a modulus of elasticity much lower than that of steel and (α + β)-Ti alloys, making them ideal for biomedical applications, where lower modulus enhances the long-term performance of the alloy [196–199]. Pure β -phase formation in the Ti-Nb system using SLM was reported by Fischer et al. [200] using of a powder mixture of Ti:Nb = 59.5:40.5 wt proportion, that is, 74:26 atom proportion. Single β -Ti-26Nb phase formation with defect-free microstructure was reported at 210 J/mm³ energy density [201]. The study also claims the possibility of α'' formation in TiNb alloys if they may contain less than 25 at.% Nb. Another study by Zhuravleva et al. [202] reported major β phase formation along with minor amount of α'' phase in a SLM Ti-40Nb alloy. Mechanical testing revealed that the elastic modulus achieved for SLM Ti-26Nb (76–77 GPa) is lower than for CP-Ti (120 GPa) but close to a Ti-26Nb solution treated ingot (70 GPa) [200]. The decrease in modulus with increase in wt.% of Nb for SLM- β alloys is in correlation with what was found for arc-melted β -Ti-36/40/42Nb alloys [203]. The total energy density during SLM was maintained at ~285 J/mm³ by using ~200 W laser power and 35 μ m/s laser speed [202]. Weinmann et al. [204] fabricated a Ti-42Nb β -alloy using two methods (sintering and SLM-printing) and compared their properties with cast Ti-6Al-4V pellets. The β -alloys fabricated by both methods were superior to Ti-6Al-4V in terms of biocompatibility and elastic behavior [204]. Fischer et al. [205] fabricated Ti-27.5Nb using direct additive laser construction, also known as CLAD Process (direct additive laser manufacturing process), and concluded that the CLAD-manufactured samples exhibited a Young's modulus of 70 \pm 4 GPa, which was higher than that of cast Ti-27.5Nb ingots. Biocompatibility tests performed on CLAD-deposited Ti-27.5Nb alloy specimens revealed significantly higher cell activity than tissue culture cast plates after 6 days of cultivation [205]. Similarly, Wang et al. [206] fabricated Ti-35Nb alloy using SLM from elemental powder mixtures, which also offers relatively low Young's modulus (~85 GPa).

Addition of Mo as β -stabilizer has shown to increase the microhardness, bending strength and modulus [207]. On increasing the wt.% of molybdenum from 0.8 to 9.9 during LENS fabrication,

the β -phase volume fraction was observed to increase from 0.07 to 0.8 vol.%, respectively [207]. At 2.6 wt%, a bimodal distribution of Widmanstätten α laths within the β matrix was achieved. Subsequently, with an increase in the weight content from 1.8 to 17 wt%, the volume fraction of β transformed from (α + β)-phase to a single β -phase [208]. Similar work by Mantri et al. [209] showcased the formation of a single β -phase during the fabrication of Ti-20 wt% V using the LENS process. In the same study, Ti-12wt% Mo yielded an (α + β)-phase mixture instead of a single β -phase [209]. However, these works failed to provide deeper insights into the mechanical behavior of these alloys.

Bhardwaj et al. [210] studied the parameter optimization for Ti-15Mo deposited by direct energy deposition (DED)-laser additive manufacturing (LAM) process. They were successful in achieving pure β -phase at 15 wt% Mo, with a modulus of 73 \pm 1.5 GPa and a yield strength of 480 \pm 42 MPa, which falls in the range of β -type Ti-(15–18)Mo wt.% solution treated and cold rolled samples studied by Zhao et al. [211]. This study opened up the path for the development of pore-free bioimplants using the DED-LAM process.

Further, Nagase et al. [212] fabricated binary alloys comprised Ti₈₀X₂₀ (X = Cr, Mo, Nb or Ta) using SLM. After fabrication, only Ti-Cr exhibited a single beta phase without unmelted particles, whereas Ti-Mo showcased β -phase formation along with unmelted particles and, conversely, Ti-Nb and Ti-Ta exhibited β and α'' martensite phases. Interestingly, in another study performed by Todai et al. [213] the addition of Nb/Cr at 20at.% ratio (i.e. the same ratio as used by Nagase et al. [212]) to titanium powder resulted in pure β -phase. A small amount of α'' martensite phase was observed in as-built Ti-20Nb alloy samples in comparison with the as-cast alloy. These studies provide an alternative for producing pure β -phase Ti alloys through SLM by mixing pure elemental powders of β -stabilizers with Ti powder, thereby circumventing the shortage of β -type prealloyed powders for AM.

Tantalum is the heaviest metal among the possible β -stabilizers, (V, Cr, Nb, Mo). Owing to its high melting point and big atomic radius, its diffusion kinetics is more sluggish than for the other elements [214]. Titanium-tantalum (TiTa) alloys with equal mass ratio (50%) were fabricated using SLM for biomedical applications [152,215]. The resulting pure β -phase samples possessed an elastic modulus of 75.77 \pm 4.04 GPa [215]. Soro et al. [216] printed porous structures based on the Schwartz primitive unit cell using Ti-25Ta and compared the mechanical properties with Ti-6Al-4V. The study included structures with three varying degrees of porosity: 25%, 42%, and 64% [216]. The Young's modulus of Ti-25Ta specimens with varying porosity was at least 32% lower than that of the corresponding porous structures made of Ti-6Al-4V.

Fig. 10. An SLM Ti-13Nb-13Zr prosthetic bridge after sand blasting. Adapted with permission provided by journal with the term (CC BY-NC-ND), dated 20th May 2020 [220]. SLM, selective laser melting.

3.2.2. Ternary β -alloys

Ternary Ti-Nb-Zr β -alloys are considered potential next-generation biomaterials as a better alternative for Ti-6Al-4V. Among the binary systems mentioned previously, Ti-Nb alloys have the lowest elastic modulus, and display shape memory behavior and hyperelasticity, thereby trumping over other binary alloys. Addition of Nb to Ti increases the phase stability of the β phase. However, with increasing Nb content the martensite transformation temperature generally decreases [217]. This issue can be addressed by addition of Sn, Ta, Pd, Zr, Mo, or Cu [217,218]. Ti-Nb-Zr alloys do not contain toxic elements (Al and V) as they are present in Ti-6Al-4V. Herein, Zr acts as a substitute for Al by providing solid-solution strengthening in Ti as an α -stabilizer, whereas Nb replaces V by acting as a β -stabilizer and provides low elastic modulus and high tensile strength [178]. In the following, different alloy variants of Ti-Nb-Zr alloys manufactured in the recent past using SLM will be discussed.

3.2.2.1. Ti-13Nb-13Zr. Zr addition in Ti alloys is aimed towards β phase stability, reduction in the elastic modulus and to improve the mechanical behavior [219]. Seramak et al. [220] attempted the fabrication of Ti-13Nb-13Zr prototype dental crown bridge prosthetics via SLM. A CAD was used by scanning the patient's mouth before fabrication. The overall density received in the fabricated components was more than 98% of the theoretical density. Fig. 10 shows the prosthetic bridge designed in their study. Their study focused on parameter and design optimization and therefore lacks mechanical, microstructure and biocompatibility analysis, which opens up a future scope to study this alloy for the required properties.

Zhou et al. [222] studied the microstructure, densification and mechanical behavior of Ti-13Nb-13Zr using SLM. The maximum densification of $\sim 9.8 \pm 0.5\%$ was achieved with 519.448 Hv (5.094 GPa) hardness and 1106 MPa tensile strength at optimized 83.33 J/mm³ energy density [222]. Obtained fatigue strength of Ti-13Nb-13Zr from SLM was also reported to be better than cast samples, owing to the finer grains, martensitic phase formation and dislocation accumulation [222].

A comparative study carried out by Zhou et al. [221] between near β , α and ($\alpha+\beta$) phases of titanium by printing CP-Ti, Ti-6Al-4V and Ti-13Nb-13Zr through SLM revealed that Ti-13Nb-13Zr demonstrates superior mechanical properties compared with the other two materials. Fig. 11 demonstrated the scanning micrographs of all three compositions with top and front view having different features. Martensitic α' hcp phase is evident in the top view of CP-Ti and Ti-6Al-4V samples (Fig. 11 a and b), whereas β grains are visible in the front section of Ti-6Al-4V sample (Fig. 11 e) surface but absent in CP-Ti (Fig. 11 d). Extreme fine α' grains were evident in both top and front sections of Ti-13Nb-13Zr sample (Fig. 11 [c and f]) The near β -alloy has the highest tensile strength-to-elastic modulus ratio, and exhibits strain-controlled fatigue strength, as well as a more stable corrosion potential when compared with pure α -Ti and ($\alpha+\beta$) phase alloys (refer Fig. 12).

3.2.2.2. Ti-18Zr-14Nb. A new near-beta Ti alloy, Ti-18Zr-14Nb, fabricated by laser powder bed fusion, has been investigated for orthopedic and dental applications [223]. Parameter optimization was performed for the following variables: laser power ($P = 125, 200, 280$ W), scanning speed ($v = 700, 950, 1200$ mm/s), and hatch spacing ($h = 80, 140, 200$ μ m). Using these parameters, samples were fabricated in the energy density input range of 9–85 J/mm³. A maximum densification ($\sim 100\%$) was obtained in the energy density range of 25–45 J/mm³ which contributed in achieving a maximum hardness value of 255 ± 10 Hv (2.501 ± 0.09 GPa) [223]. Postprocessing heat treatment of the fully dense samples was

performed at 400–700 °C for 30 min, followed by water quenching. The resulting samples showed higher hardness values in the side surfaces as compared with the top surface. This higher hardness value at the sides was attributed to the microstructure anisotropy development during the fabrication. Microhardness of the samples annealed at 400 °C was found with increased values, which was assumed due to the ω -phase precipitation. After annealing at 500 °C, a decrease in microhardness at both the top and side surfaces was observed with higher hardness at sides. A slight increase with almost similar values at both top and sides were attained for the samples annealed at 700 °C [223].

Build rate was also suggested to have a significant role along with the energy density optimization to achieve best surface finish. With the fact that that higher surface roughness occurs with the higher build rate, this study suggested 10–25 cm³/h as a build rate range to achieve best surface finish. More than this build rate (>25 cm³/h) triggered coarser surface finish, compromising the component properties [223]. A set of energy density and build rate can be used to achieve full densification by following Fig. 16. Although this study focused on the surface behavior, densification and hardness of the samples at different process conditions in detail but did not address the change in intrinsic compressive strength, modulus or biocompatibility of the alloy with change in process parameters, which opens up a scope to study the other properties of this alloy for biomedical application [223].

3.2.2.3. Ti-35Zr-28Nb. Li et al. [224] demonstrated successful fabrication of bulk and porous (FCCZ structure (face centered cubic unit cell with longitudinal struts) and FBCCZ structure (face and body centered cubic unit cell with longitudinal struts)) and bulk β -type Ti-35Zr-28Nb specimens for orthopedic applications at a laser power of 140 W and an energy density of 80 J/mm³. Scaffolds of FCCZ structures (face centered unit cell with longitudinal struts) with 83% porosity and FBCCZ structures (face and body centered unit cell with longitudinal struts) were prepared with a resulting low elastic modulus of ~ 1 GPa and plateau strength of 8–58 MPa [224]. The obtained values were found to have a close values as for trabecular bone. Bulk sample with a maximum 98% of theoretical density was fabricated at optimum conditions by SLM. Phase analysis confirmed the presence of only β phase in both longitudinal and transverse directions. The XRD patterns showing the single β phase in as received powder and SLMed samples in both the directions are shown in Fig. 13. The elastic modulus of bulk in longitudinal and transverse directions was almost same and calculated as $57 \pm 1.8\%$ GPa and 60.2 ± 2.0 GPa, respectively, whereas higher yield strength (768 ± 30 MPa) in transverse direction was observed as compared in longitudinal direction (612 ± 29 MPa) [224].

In case of porous structures (FCCZ and FBCCZ), both the modulus and plateau strength were found more longitudinal direction than the transvers direction due to the additional longitudinal struts in both the structures. When compared both the structures, FBCCZ was found to show more modulus and more plateau strength than the FCCZ structure due to comparative higher porosity level in FCCZ. Corrosion study in Hank's solution confirmed the passive layer formation on all the samples with similar passive behavior in both longitudinal and transverse directions. The presence of Zr and Nb were reported to form oxide layers on the surface leading to an easier passivation at lower potential values. In addition, *in vitro* biocompatibility tests using osteoblast-like cells (SaOS2) revealed that both fcc and bcc structures had more than 95% viable cells, with good biocompatibility [224].

Fig. 11. Scanning Electron micrographs of SLM-fabricated samples of (a, d) CP-Ti (b, e) Ti-6Al-4V, and (c, f) Ti-13Nb-13Zr where (a–c) shows top view and (d–f) shows front view. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844080951000 dated 8th 2020 [221]. SLM, selective laser melting.

Fig. 12. (a) Processing map for Ti-Zr-Nb alloy showing the different set (zones) of parameters with corresponding μ -computed tomography (CT) images: (b) I, (c) II, (d) III and (e) IV. (Here, % is used to show relative densification, and R_a is used to represent surface roughness at top surface). Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844081187274 dated 8th June 2020 [223].

3.2.3. Quaternary β -alloys

For further enhancing the mechanical and intrinsic properties of ternary alloys, addition of a fourth element was proposed.

3.2.3.1. Titanium-niobium-zirconium-X(Sn/Ta) β -alloys

3.2.3.1.1. Ti-24Nb-4Zr-8Sn (Ti2448). Recent studies have proved the strong impact of Zr and Sn additions in suppressing the α'' martensitic transformation of Ti-Nb alloys [225]. The addition of optimum Sn contents provides β -phase stability without increasing the elastic modulus of the alloy [170]. SLM-Ti2448 exhibits superior mechanical properties (yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and uniform elongation) outperforming conventional forged material, rendering AM a promising alternative to conventional casting methods for dental and orthopedic applications [226]. Hernandez et al. [227] fabricated bulk samples from β -phase Ti-

24Nb-4Zr-7.9Sn powder in an upgraded EBM machine constituting heat shields to maintain a preheating temperature of 250 °C in the building chamber. The resulting EBM samples contained a majority of single β -phase along with a diminutive amount of α'' martensite, which was untraceable in XRD. On the contrary, Liu et al. [228] printed porous structures using Ti2448 powder with a building plate temperature of ~500 °C, which resulted in an (α + β) phase mixture (in significant amount as detected by XRD) rather than a pure β -phase. This discrepancy in phase formation was considered to be a consequence of long exposure at high temperatures resulting in phase transformation during the building process. Printed porous samples demonstrated twice the strength-to-modulus ratio when compared with conventional Ti-6Al-4V with same architecture [228]. In another study by Liu et al. [229], a comparative analysis for Ti2448 manufactured by SLM and EBM for

Fig. 13. X-ray diffraction patterns of Ti-35Zr-28Nb alloy powder (a) and SLMed samples in longitudinal (b) and transverse directions (c). Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844090449178 dated 8th June 2020 [224]. SLM, selective laser melting.

application in joint replacements was carried out. This study was in agreement with the previous findings, suggesting that a change in the temperature of the building platform results in phase transformation, that is, samples built by EBM at temperatures of $\sim 400\text{--}500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ showed $(\alpha+\beta)$ -phase, whereas SLM-built samples at $\sim 200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ resulted in pure β -phase. These findings suggest that the SLM samples cooled faster than their EBM counterparts, resulting in fine parallel β -dendrites. In addition, the SLM samples contained 10 times more defects (pores) than the EBM specimens due to entrapment of tin vapor resulting from the small spot size of the laser and faster quenching upon cooling. The evaporation and entrapment of tin due to change in scanning speed resulted in the generation of defects/pores in the EBM samples. Liu et al. [179] observed the same by using 5 different scanning speeds of 500, 750, 1000, 1250, and 1500 mm/s in their experiments. The average pore size decreases suddenly between 500 and 750 mm/s and then increases with increasing scan speed. Surprisingly, the strut thickness in the building direction (Z-direction) decreased with increase in scanning speed for EBM. These results are in agreement with their previous reports, where a lower range of scanning speeds (150, 300, 600, and 900 mm/s) were used for EBM [228]. However, the inference of a general relationship between average pore size and scanning speed is disputable and inconclusive as well as requires further investigations.

In a study on rhombic dodecahedral structures composed of β -type Ti2448, fabricated using EBM, Liu et al. [230] established an inversely proportional relationship between the amount of porosity and Young's modulus. For porosities of 67.9%, 72.5%, 75.0%, 77.4%, 79.5%, and 91.2%, they found Young's moduli of approximately 1.7, 1.4, 1.2, 1.0, 0.9, and 0.4 GPa [230]. Besides, improved superelastic properties of the samples were reported with increasing porosity level. In addition, Ti2448 porous specimens displayed higher normalized fatigue strength and bigger plastic zones than Ti-6Al-4V.

In a similar study, porous, cubic, rhombic dodecahedron and topology optimized G_7 structures were fabricated using SLM of Ti2448 by the same group [231]. Overall, the porous structures displayed modulus values well within the range of native bone; the rhombic dodecahedron had the lowest modulus of 1.13 GPa, whereas topology optimized G_7 structures exhibited 2.3 GPa and cubic structures 3.3 GPa, respectively. The difference in energy

distribution of all three structures was reported due to different stress distribution and local stress concentration. Microstructure analysis revealed the formation of a pure β -phase, which is ideal for biomedical applications. Optimized and cubic structures have shown $\sim 58\text{ MPa}$ and $\sim 56\text{ MPa}$ compression strength with $\sim 15\%$ and $\sim 6\%$ deformation strain respectively, whereas rhombic dodecahedron structure showed best ductility ($>30\%$) but with a lowest compressive strength. This study mostly dealt with the plastic and elastic energy absorption for the porous structures correlated with slip bands and dislocation motion [231].

Zhang et al. [8] fabricated an acetabular cup (an example is shown in Fig. 14) made of Ti2448 alloy by SLM. The increase in incident laser energy or decreasing the laser scan speed has reported good to achieve near full densification more than 99% theoretical density at 200 W laser power without any post-processing [8]. Higher hardness retained at the scan speed less than 300 mm/s even if the density decreases. The decrease in density attributes to the poor surface finish but full densification from internally which reduced the overall density value when averaged. Therefore, this study suggests the need of acceptable surface finish along with the internal densification by optimizing the laser parameters. The suggested range lies between 300 and 600 mm/s scan speeds. Considering the overall cost and other parameters, fabrication of acetabular cup in the study was carried out at 550 mm/s [8].

SLM fabricated samples showed similar mechanical properties as the conventional samples where the modulus and ultimate tensile strength has been reported (Zhang et al. [232]) as 46 GPa and 830 MPa, respectively, for hot rolled samples and 55 GPa and 755 MPa, respectively, for hot forged samples (Li et al. [233]). In this study, the SLM fabricated samples showed a close mechanical behavior with $53 \pm 1\text{ GPa}$ modulus and $665 \pm 18\text{ MPa}$ ultimate tensile strength. Although the data lack phase representation of pure β -phase, a prototype for future use of Ti2448 was successfully fabricated as primary step, the biocompatibility test of the SLMed samples can be studied in future for biomedical applications [8].

3.2.3.1.2. *Ti-35Nb-2Ta-3Zr*. Hafeez et al. [234] fabricated β -type Ti-35Nb-2Ta-3Zr alloy (Ti3523) specimens using SLS. The parameters used for fabrication were as follows: laser power of 325 W

Fig. 14. A precise acetabular cup fabricated by SLM method (laser power 200W, scan speed 550 mm/s). Inset shows the higher resolution scaffold created on the surface with the aim to improve bone in-growth. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4844090588837 dated 8th June 2020 [8]. SLM, selective laser melting.

with a scan speed of 1100 mm/s and layer thickness of 0.03 mm. The fabricated Ti3523 samples possessed an enhanced recoverable strain of 4.8% at the maximum applied strain of 27% compared with the cast counterpart, whereas the elastic recovery rate of a solution treated Ti3523 cast sample has been reported around 35% [235]. The enhanced properties were attributed to the formation of Type I twin martensite inside the β -phase. The occurrence of twin martensite was accredited to different transformation mechanisms taking place during the deformation. A large dislocation density and dislocation tangling along the grain boundaries were found responsible for heterogeneous β phase nucleation during SLS, enhancing the formation of twin martensite, stress-induced ω structure and the v-shaped or zigzag-shaped formation of $\{112\} <111>_b$ twins [234].

3.2.3.1.3. *Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr*. Luo et al. [236] manufactured bulk specimens and lattice structures of Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr via SLM using a laser power of 200 W, a layer thickness of 50 μm and an exposure time of 165 μs . Optimization of parameters resulted in having almost full densification (>99%) in bulk part. As prepared samples were able to achieve ~680 MPa tensile strength, ~64.2 GPa elastic modulus, ~15.3% elongation, and 140 MPa fatigue limit. The lattice structure made with 77.23 vol.% porosity showed an integral yield strength of ~15.7 MPa [236]. From microstructure characterization, it was concluded that the SLMed Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr samples contained mostly a β -rich phase along with a small amount of α -phase. In addition, the dense Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr alloy showed enhanced biocompatibility compared with Ti-6Al-4V when tested with a Mouse fibroblast cell line (L929). The yield strength of SLMed TNZT in a range of 15.7–520 MPa was obtained in lattice structures [236].

3.2.3.2. Titanium-vandium-iron-aluminum β -alloys

3.2.3.2.1. *Ti-10V-2Fe-3Al*. Qiu and Liu [237] adapted a pulsed laser mode instead of a continuous mode upon SLM for better microstructural control of a Ti-10V-2Fe-3Al alloy. This study focussed on parameter optimization to obtain a fine microstructure for enhanced mechanical properties. A laser power of 200 W was found to provide the finest grains. Increasing the power above this value resulted in increased grain size, but the grain morphology did not significantly change with variation of laser power and exposure time. The presence of ω phase along with β -phase was observed in all samples. The formation of α -phase was also observed at higher energy densities. The variation in phase formation and volume fraction of the constituent phases was solely attributed to the high heating and cooling rates during processing along with a pulsed heating effect. Deformation in α -free samples occurred via both slip and twinning, showcasing higher strength, while coarse-grained α -containing samples underwent only localized plastic deformation inside the β matrix resulting in cleavage fracture without ductility during mechanical testing. In the case of the formation of a hybrid grain structure, intergranular fracture and poor ductility was observed [237].

3.2.3.2.2. *Ti-1Al-8V-5Fe (Ti-185)*. Fabrication of Ti-1Al-8V-5Fe (Ti-185) using conventional casting and forging methods is not usually not feasible due to segregation of Fe and the formation of β -fleck (β -phase regions enriched with β stabilizing elements) [182]. However, AM was successfully used for printing of Ti-1Al-8V-5Fe, as it overcomes the limitations of the conventional production methods. SLM of Ti-1Al-8V-5Fe powder using a laser power of 370 W, a scanning speed of 1035 mm/s, and a layer thickness of 60 μm followed by heat treatment at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min and water quenching resulted in a pure β -phase structure [238]. In contrast, as-built samples without heat treatment resulted in an (α + β)-phase mixture [238]. A proposed temperature-time profile for the Ti-185 alloy during SLM followed by a postheat treatment is shown in Fig. 15 [238]. There are a few other β -alloys comprised multiple

elements prepared by AM methods for biomedical applications. One of the studies reported on the formation of pure β -phase in Ti-3Al-8V-6Cr-4Zr-4Mo using SLM with a higher fracture toughness and a three times larger ductility than Ti-6Al-4V [239]. Some of the novel techniques used for fabrication of β -alloys involves welding with some other alloys and heat treatments. Table 4 summarizes the elastic moduli and biocompatibility of β -alloys exhibiting various structures, as reported in the literature. The unit cells and structures used for fabricating porous alloy parts through SLM are listed in Table 5.

4. Ti matrix composites based on laser manufacturing

In general, metal matrix composites (MMCs) are developed for improving mechanical, corrosion and thermal behavior as compared with the base metal or alloys for specific applications [240–242]. They can either have continuous or intermittent distribution of reinforcements in the matrix, where the reinforcement may be in any form including whiskers, fibers, or particles [243–246]. The incorporation of reinforcements can be carried out either by *in situ* or *ex situ* methods, depending on the processing route. *In situ* MMCs show better thermal stability and interfacial bonding than *ex situ* MMCs [247–249]. Better interfacial bonding also helps in increasing the mechanical properties. In MMCs, various reinforcements such as Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 , Si_3N_4 , SiC, TiB_2 , Cr_3C_2 , and so on, are used, depending on the matrix material, the used processing route and the desired properties [250–252]. Some reinforcements such as TiB and TiC fall in the category of *ex situ* composites, whereas other compounds such as SiC and TiB_2 used as reinforcements that react with the Ti matrix and form strong TiC and TiB interfaces, respectively, are categorized as *in situ* composites. Elements such as B and C also result in enhanced properties when added in the Ti matrix. Before the selection of a reinforcement material, the information of certain properties such as thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) and elastic modulus is important to get a strong bond with the matrix [253–258]. Weak interface and thermal stresses may occur if there is a large difference of elastic modulus or TEC values between the matrix and reinforcement material. Such cases end in material failure during application [259]. Table 6 shows the TEC and modulus values of the reinforcement particles as compared with commercially available pure Ti and Ti-6Al-4V alloys.

Generally, Ti and its alloys have poor hardness and wear resistance [262]. Applications of Ti-based materials can be extended by altering composition and processing routes, which can enhance the properties beyond the currently available Ti alloys [263]. In this

Fig. 15. Schematic representation of the complex temperature-time profile for the Ti-185 alloy during AM. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833071500448 dated 20th May 2020 [238].

Table 4
Compressive properties of porous β -Ti alloys for biomedical applications.

S. No	Alloy	Structure	Method Phase	E (GPa)	Biocompatibility	Reference
1.	Ti-26Nb	Solid	SLM Pure β phase	77.2 \pm 0.4	NA	[200]
2.	Ti-40Nb	Solid	SLM Major β -phase + 11 \pm 5% α Phase	33 \pm 2	60% viable compared with casted Ti-40Nb	[202]
3.	Ti-42Nb	Solid	SLM Pure β phase	60.8	>92% cell viability compared with tissue culture plate and 21% more than Ti-6Al-4V	[204]
4.	Ti-25Ta	DENSE Schwartz primitive (Porosity 25%) Schwartz primitive (Porosity 42%) Schwartz primitive (Porosity 64%)	SLM α'' within β prior grains	73.5 \pm 1.8 36.1 \pm 2.2 23.3 \pm 1.5 14.3 \pm 0.7	NA	[216]
5.	TiTa	Solid	SLM Pure β phase	75.77 \pm 4.04	NA	[215]
6.	Ti-35Zr-28Nb	Porous FCC(83% porosity) Porous bcc (50% Porosity)	SLM β phase crystal structure	1.1 \pm 0.1 1.3 \pm 0.1	>95% cell viability compared with tissue culture plate	[224]
7.	Ti-24Nb-4Zr-7.9Sn	Solid	SLM Claim β (lacks XRD)	57.0 \pm 1.8 53 \pm 1	NA	[8]
8.	Ti-24Nb-4Zr-7.9Sn	Solid	EBM Majority β -phase + diminutive traces of α'' -martensite	-	NA	[227]
9.	Ti-24Nb-4Zr-8Sn (Ti2448)	Rhombic dodecahedron structure (75% porosity)	SLM Pure β phase after annealing	-0.95 \pm 0.05	NA	[229]
10.	Ti2448	G_structure7 (70% porosity)	EBM α + β	-1.34 \pm 0.04	NA	[228]
11.	Ti2448	Rhombic dodecahedron (72.5%)	EBM Pure β phase after annealing	0.7 \pm 0.1	NA	[230]
12.	Ti2448	Rhombic dodecahedron (Porosity 75%) Topology optimized (Porosity 75%) Cubic (Porosity 75%)	SLM Pure β phase	-1.44 \pm 0.2 -1.13 -2.3 -3.3	NA	[231]
13.	Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr	Dense Rhombic dodecahedron (Porosity 77.23%)	SLM B rich phase with α -phase in low amount	59.5 0.79	Dense Ti-30Nb-5Ta-3Zr is 6% more biocompatible than Ti-6Al-4V	[236]
14.	Ti-3Al-8V-6Cr-4Zr-4Mo	Solid	SLM Pure β phase	68.3 \pm 5.0	NA	[239]

SLM, selective laser melting; EBM, electron beam melting; bcc, body-centered cubic.

direction, the development of titanium matrix composites can be an alternative to achieve superior properties compared with CP-Ti and Ti alloys. Ti-based alloys, owing to their low thermal conductivity and high chemical reactivity, often cause undesired reactions that have deleterious effects on their machinability [264]. Careful processing of titanium matrix composites (TMCs) can help avoiding such undesired reactions. Addition of hard ceramic particles in the Ti matrix has reportedly improved the mechanical properties and abrasion resistance [81]. For TMCs, both the physical and chemical attributes of matrix and reinforcement can affect the processing, as well as the final properties. Different surface modification methods such as laser surface alloying, laser melt injection, and laser cladding have also been used on bulk TMCs manufactured via powder metallurgy (P/M), casting and chemical routes [81,82].

A variety of reinforcement materials can be used to improve the mechanical properties of TMCs, but the majority of studies report only TiB and TiC particles as reinforcement materials in Ti alloys [260,261,265–268]. Both these reinforcements show good thermal conductivity, chemical compatibility, high modulus and density close to Ti metal, which makes them an appropriate choice as reinforcement. For TiC-reinforced Ti matrix composites, various powder combinations such as Ti/TiC, Ti/Al/C or Ti/SiC can be used for different AM technique, whereas TiB reinforcement can be achieved mostly by specifically using SLM and LENS techniques [41,143,269–271]. Different AM techniques used for TMCs are listed

in Tables 7 and 8 has concluded all the process parameters used for composite preparation by SLM, including powder preparation and SLM parameters.

4.1. α and (α + β)-Ti matrix composites

α and (α + β)-Ti alloys have been used for several years for important structural applications despite they have proven unsatisfactory for heavily loaded structures due to inadequate yield strength [182]. Various studies have been reported on different reinforcement additions in α and (α + β)-Ti base alloys to improve their strength [182]. The following section provides a compilation of the most significant efforts resulting in improved mechanical properties, oxidation and corrosion resistance and structural behavior by either *in situ* or *ex situ* reinforcement addition during SLM of Ti-based materials. For reinforcement addition, ball milling is the most preferred technique to obtain a uniform mixture of powders [298].

4.1.1. Ti-TiC composites

Commercial purity Ti has been the most widely used material for high specific strength and corrosion resistance applications for the longest time [299]. Li et al. [297] studied SLM of a 1% Mo₂C reinforced CP-Ti matrix composite. Addition of TiC particles in different concentrations to fabricate Ti-TiC composites has also

Table 5
Overview of different structures and their unit cells fabricated for biomedical applications.

S.No.	Structure name	Unit cell	Lattice	Adapted with the permission
1.	Schwartz primitive (porosity 25%)		Under the license no. 4833080574380 [216]	
2.	Schwartz primitive (porosity 42%)			
3.	Schwartz primitive (porosity 64%)			
4.	FCC (porosity 83%)		Under the license no. 4833080918058 [224]	
5.	bcc (porosity 50%)			
6.	Rhombicd odecahedron structure (porosity 72.5%, *75 **77.23)		[230] * [229,231] ** [236] Under the license no. 4833090047818 [231]	
7.	G_structure7 (porosity 70%)		Under the license no. 4833081319927 [228]	
8.	Topology optimized (porosity 75%)		Under the license no. 4833090047818 [231]	
9.	Cubic (porosity 75%)			

bcc, body centered cubic.

Table 6
Different reinforcements and their properties [260,261].

Material	TEC (thermal expansion coefficient) ($\times 10^{-6}/K$)	Young's modulus (GPa)
Pure Ti	8.8	105
Ti-6Al-4V	8.8	110
Al ₂ O ₃	8.1	350
TiB ₂	6.2–6.4	529–540
TiC	7.4	460
TiB	8.6	550
B ₄ C	4.5	449
SiC	4.3	420
TiN	9.3	250
Si ₃ N ₄	3.2	320

Table 7
Different AM techniques used for different Ti matrix composites.

Powder mixture	Matrix	Reinforcement	Fabrication method	References
Ti and TiC	Ti	TiC	SLM	[117,272]
Ti and TiC	Ti	TiC	LPD	[273]
Ti, Al and graphite powder	Ti(Al) solid solution	TiC	SLM	[274]
Ti and SiC	Ti	TiC	SLM	[265]
Ti and TiB ₂	Ti	TiB	SLM	[4]
Ti and B powders	Ti	TiB	LENS	[275]
Ti-6Al-4V and B	Ti-6Al-4V	TiB	DLD	[276]
Ti-6Al-4V and B	Ti-6Al-4V	TiB	LENS	[277]
Ti-6Al-4V and TiB ₂ powders	Ti-6Al-4V	TiB	DLF	[278]
TNZZT and TiB ₂	TNZZT	TiB	LENS	[279]
Ti and B ₄ C	Ti	TiB and TiC	DLD	[268]
Ti and SiC	Ti	TiC, unmelt SiC, TiSi ₂ , Ti ₅ Si ₃	LENS	[280]
Ti and Si ₃ N ₄	Ti	TiN	SLM	[281]
Ti and TiB ₂	Ti	TiB	SLM	[282]
Ti-6Al-4V and TiN	Ti-6Al-4V	TiN	LENS	[283]
Ti-6Al-4V and BN	Ti-6Al-4V	TiB and TiN	LENS	[284]
Ti and Ta	Ti	Ta	SLM	[152]
Ti-6Al-4V and Mo	Ti-6Al-4V	Mo	SLM	[285]

SLM, selective laser melting; LENS, laser engineered net shaping.

been examined systematically [297]. Commercial purity Ti is known for its corrosion resistance and service durability, but it often does not meet the property requirements concerning strength, wear resistance and hardness [300]. This study [297] reported the β -Ti phase as Mo-rich region and discussed the effect of laser power on the microstructural evolution. In another investigation, the dependence of the microstructure evolution on densification, wear resistance and hardness was evaluated [117]. Ball milling, instead of simple mixing of the respective powders of a Ti-15%TiC powder mixture, resulted in higher densification in the

processed composites [298]. Table 9 shows various processing parameters that were optimized for achieving superior densification and other properties. The optimization of various processing conditions shows that the highest relative density of around 98% can be achieved at an energy density of 360 J/mm³. At lower energy densities around 90 J/mm³, the relative density decreased to 91%. The dispersion and nature of the TiC phase were reported to depend mostly on the applied energy density [301].

At lower energy densities (180 J/mm³ and 90–120 J/mm³), homogenous and fine TiC reinforcements were observed in the form

Fig. 16. Microstructures of Ti-15%TiC at different applied energy densities (a and e) 360 J/mm³; (c and h) 120 J/mm³ and (d) 90 J/mm³ [117]. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833090240916 dated 20th May 2020 [81].

Table 8

Powder preparation and SLM parameters for the fabrication of different TMCs.

Details of used powders	Initial composition	Reinforcement phase formation	Ball to powder ratio (BPR)	Milling time (h)	RPM	Laser parameters					Reference
						Scan speed	Laser power	Powder layer thickness	Hatch spacing	Laser spot diameter	
> TiC (average diameter 45 μm, near spherical)	Ti-5wt.% TiC	TiC	8:1	4	300	200 mm/s	100 W	50 μm	70 μm	100 μm	[286]
> Ti (average diameter 25 μm, spherical)											
> Ti (mean particle size 30 μm, polygonal structure),	Ti-Si ₃ N ₄ (75.45:24.55wt%)	Ti ₅ Si ₃	10:1	8	250	0.10 m/s	900 W	0.15 mm	0.15 mm	0.30 mm	[287]
> Si ₃ N ₄ (average 4 μm size, irregular shape)											
> Ti (mean size 30 μm, irregular shape),	50 at.% Ti, 25 at.% Al,	TiC	10:1	32	250	0.10 m/s	700 –900 W	0.15 mm	0.15 mm	0.30 mm	[288]
> Al (average 16 μm mean size, Irregular shape)	25 at.% C										
> Pure graphite C (mean 30 μm size)											
> Ti-6Al-4V (20–70 μm range, D ₅₀ ~37.3 μm, spherical shaped)	-Ti-6Al-4V –1 wt.% TiB ₂	TiB	4:1	4	200	300 mm/s	240 W	0.05 mm	0.12 mm	0.08 mm	[289]
> TiB ₂ (D ₅₀ ~2.71 μm, irregular polygon shaped)	- Ti-6Al-4V –2 wt.% TiB ₂										
> CP-Ti (d ₅₀ ~49 μm)	Ti-5 wt.% TiB ₂	TiB	5:1	2/4	200	150 mm/s	180 W	100 μm	100 μm	80 μm	[282]
> TiB ₂ (d ₅₀ ~3.5–6 μm)											
> CP-Ti (d ₅₀ ~48.69 μm)	Ti-5 wt.% TiB ₂	TiB	5:1	1–4	200	118–154 mm/s	165 –185 W	100 μm	100 μm	80 μm	[51]
> TiB ₂ (d ₅₀ ~3.5–6 μm)											
> Ti (mean size 45 μm, poly-angular structured)	Ti-SiC (76.2:23.8 wt%)	Ti ₅ Si ₃	10:1	15	300	0.1/0.2/0.3/0.4 m/s	80 W	50 μm	50 μm	70 μm	[290]
> SiC (average size 13 μm, irregular shaped)											
> Ti (30 μm, polygonal),	- Ti-Si ₃ N ₄ (75.45:24.55)	TiN	10:1	10	250	200 mm/s	1000 W	100 μm	0.15 mm	0.30 mm	[291]
> Si ₃ N ₄ (4 μm, irregular shaped)	- Ti-Si ₃ N ₄										
> RE-Si-Fe (20 μm, near spherical)	(75.45:24.5 + 3% RE-Si-Fe										
> Ti (-50 + 20 μm, poly-angular structure)	Ti-xTiB ₂ (x = 5, 10 and 15 vol.%)	TiB	–	24	–	0.5–10 cm/s	10–100 W	0.1 mm	70 mm	70 mm	[292]
> TiB ₂ (2–10 μm)											
> Ti (mean diameter 22.5 μm, spherical)	Ti-15%TiC	TiC	5:1	4	200	0.1/0.2/0.3/0.4 m/s	90 W	50 μm	50 μm	70 μm	[117]
> TiC (average size 50 nm, near spherical)											
> CP-Ti (average particle size ~43.5 μm, spherical)	Ti-Ta (1:1)	–	–	12	60	400 mm/s	360 W	50 μm	0.125 mm	80 μm	[152]
> Ta powder (average particle size ~44 μm, Irregular shaped)											
> CP-Ti (particle size 15–45 μm, spherical)	CP-Ti-5 wt.% B ₄ C	TiB + TiC	1:1	2	200	800 mm/s	130 –250 W	30 μm	50 μm	70 μm	[293]
> B ₄ C (mean particle size 5 μm, polyhedron shaped)											
> Ti grade 2 alloy (particle size range ~35 + 25 μm, spherical)	Ti-xSiC (x = 20, 30, 40 wt %)	TiC _x , Ti ₅ Si ₃ C _x , TiSi ₂ , SiC	–	–	–	120 mm/s	50 and 80 W	50 μm	–	70 μm	[294]
> SiC, F1200 grade (1–6 μm grain size, acicular powder)											
> Ti (average diameter 22.5 μm, spherical)	Ti-xTiC (7.5, 12.5, 17.5 and 22.5 wt%)	TiC	5:1	4	200	0.3 m/s	90 W	50 μm	50 μm	70 μm	[272]
> TiC (average diameter 50 nm, near spherical)											
> CP-Ti (D ₅₀ ~30.8 μm, near spherical)	CP-Ti-xHA (x = 2 and 5 wt %)	Ti ₅ P ₃ , Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ , Ti _x O, CaTiO ₃	5:1	7	150	1000 mm/s	240 W	30 μm	80 μm	100 μm	[172]
> Hydroxyapatite HA (mean particle size 50 nm)											
> CP-Ti (average particle size ~ 30.1 μm, near spherical shaped)	CP-Ti-xHA (x = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 wt%)	Ti ₆ O, CaTiO ₃ , Ti ₅ P ₃ , Ca ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	5:1	7	150	1000 mm/s	240 W	30 μm	0.07 mm	100 μm	[295]
> Nano HA powder (<100 nm)											
> Ti-6Al-4V (spherical)	Ti-6Al-4V +5 wt% B ₄ C	TiB + TiC	5:1	1.5	200	1000 mm/s	200, 250, 300 W	40 μm	100 μm	100 μm	[296]
> B ₄ C (Irregular)											
> CP Ti (15–45 μm),	CP Ti+1 vol.% MO ₂ C	–	–	4	–	225–325 mm/s and 1400 –1800 mm/s	50 and 250 W	30 μm	60 μm	–	[297]
> ~3.5 μm MO ₂ C											

RE, rare earth

Table 9

Process parameters used for SLM of Ti matrix composites and their respective densities [32,81].

Composition	Scanning speed (mm/s)	Hatch distance (μm)	Laser power (W)	Layer thickness (μm)	Relative densification (%)	Reference
Ti-5%B ₄ C	800	50	130–250	30	–	[293]
Ti-2wt.%CrB ₂	1000–2000	–	175	50	97.5	[300]
Ti-2-5wt.%HA	1000	80	240	30	–	[172]
Ti6Al7Nb-2 vol.%HA	–	100	50–200	50	97	[302]
Ti6Al7Nb-5 vol.%HA	–	100	50–200	50	95	[302]
Ti-22.8wt%SiC	100–400	50	80	50	96.9	[290]
Ti-24.55 wt%Si ₃ N ₄	100–400	150	1000	100	97.7	[281]
Ti-5wt.%TiB ₂	118–154	100	165–185	100	99.5	[286]
Ti-5wt.%TiC	200	70	100	50	98.2	[272]
Ti-7.5wt%TiC	300	50	90	50	>98.3	[272]
Ti-12.5wt%TiC	300	50	90	50	98.3	[272]
Ti-15wt%TiC	100–400	50	90	50	>97	[117]
Ti-17.5wt%TiC	300	50	90	50	>97.2	[272]
Ti-22.5wt%TiC	300	50	90	50	94.7	[272]
Ti45Al2Cr5Nb-(1-3wt%)TiB ₂	800	100	300	30	85.1–92.2	[303]
Ti45Al2Cr5Nb-1wt.%TiB ₂	700	80–140	250	50	94	[304]

SLM, selective laser melting.

of TiC whiskers. At maximum energy density, a uniform distribution of TiC with dendrite morphology was found. The variation in microstructure with respect to the energy density as observed in the study is shown in Fig. 8. Maximum hardness and elastic modulus were found at 120 J/mm³. This is because of the formation of TiC reinforcement at nanoscale. The wear resistance was also found to reach a maximum at a similar energy density. The aforementioned properties degraded when the energy density was increased up to 360 J/mm³. This shows that the microstructure developing at different processing conditions directly influences the densification and, thus, also the mechanical properties. In another investigation [272], TiC reinforcements (5, 7.5, 12.5, 17.5, and 22.5 wt%) were added in different amounts to the Ti matrix to manufacture Ti-TiC composites by SLM. Composites containing 7.5 and 12.5 wt% TiC had a homogenous microstructure and a relative density higher than 98%. Higher reinforcement contents above this limit resulted in a heterogeneous microstructure, which directly affected the densification. Therefore, the density of the 17.5 and 22.5 wt% reinforced composites decreased to 97.2 and 94.7%, respectively. An increase in the reinforcement content beyond a critical limit resulted in decreased density due to the increased difficulty to melt and consolidate both Ti and TiC together. Dissolution/precipitation processes resulted in heterogeneous nucleation and grain growth of TiC. For 7.5 wt% TiC, a uniform reinforcement distribution was observed with the presence of lamellar structured TiC. Up to 12.5 wt% TiC, more uniformity and microstructure refinement was found. For 17.5 wt%, agglomeration of highly dense TiC particles resulted in decreased densification and for 22.5 wt% TiC, a network with dendritic microstructure has been reported. This change in microstructure also affected the mechanical and wear properties of the final composites [272]. A minimum wear rate was evident for the composites with 7.5 and 12.5 wt% TiC reinforcements as compared to other composites. Similarly, the microhardness was also found to be maximum (577 Hv [5.659 GPa]) for the 12.5 wt% TiC samples, which is significantly higher than that of SLM-processed CP-Ti (261 Hv [2.56 GPa]). Increasing the TiC concentration up to 22.5 wt% resulted in a hardness reduction down to a value of 412 Hv (4.04 GPa). These findings indicate that maximum densification along with superior mechanical properties can be achieved in Ti-TiC composites when the reinforcement proportion is in the range of 12.5–15 wt%. Beyond, inadequate densification, absence of nanoscale TiC phase and the formation of defects in the microstructure deteriorate the performance of the composites. In another work [286], 5 wt% TiC

were found to improve the tensile strength up to 914 MPa with a slight reduction in ductility.

He et al. [286] also used ball milling for mixing the powders before fabrication via selective laser melting. In their study, initial spherical Ti (d ~ 25 μm) powder and near spherical TiC (~45 nm) were mixed together for 4 h at 300 RPM. Morphology of the ball milled powder revealed almost spherical powder particles with no apparent change in mean size, which is shown in Fig. 17 (a) [286]. In a similar study reported by Gu et al. [287], calculated amount of polygonal Ti (d ~ 30 μm) and irregular Si₃N₄ (4 μm) powders were milled for 8 h at 250 RPM. The milled powders (Fig. 17 (b)) were found to be more uniform and refined, exhibiting a particle size of ~2.5 μm [287].

In situ fabrication of TiC phase in a Ti matrix using SLM was reported by Gu et al. [290], who studied the effect of different SLM parameters on the densification of Ti-TiC/Ti₅Si₃ composites. Increasing the applied energy density η from 0.2 to 0.267 kJ/m resulted in an increase in densification from 91.6 to 95.7%, which further increased up to a maximum of 96.9% on increasing η up to 0.4 kJ/m. The corresponding microstructure for 0.2 kJ/m η condition samples was found to consist of a number of small-sized interlayer pores with an average size of ~20 μm . A microstructure without pores and cracks was observed for $\eta \geq 0.267$ kJ/m. When the energy density was increased to 0.8 kJ/m, a sharp decrease in density to 87.2% was reported. The microstructure at this condition contained interconnected cracks of a few millimeters in length, in a direction normal to the 2D layers. Microhardness and wear resistance are dependent on the densification and, accordingly, a maximum microhardness of 980.3 Hv_{0.2} (9.611 GPa) along with superior wear performance was reported at 0.4 kJ/m energy density. The effect of scan speed and energy density on the microstructure of the printed composite is illustrated in Fig. 18. At low η and high scan speed (≥ 0.3 m/s), TiC has formed uniformly in form of dendrites within Ti₅Si₃.

Increasing the laser energy density by lowering the scan speed to 0.2 m/s resulted in refined dendrite structures. The average length of the dendrite trunks decreased from 8.5 to 10.0 μm to about 4.5 μm , whereas the primary dendrite arm size decreased from 0.8 to 0.9 μm to 0.4 μm . The primary arm spacing also decreased from 0.15 to 0.12 μm . The change in parameter settings also resulted in a change of the microstructure. At a lower scan speed of ~0.1 m/s and an energy density ~0.8 kJ/m, a large degree of dendrite coarsening was observed in a uniform fashion. A three- to five-fold increase in the size of dendrite trunks and arms was

observed, which could be correlated with deteriorated mechanical properties.

4.1.2. *In situ* Ti-TiB composites

Another highly useful and widely studied reinforcement for Ti matrix composites is TiB [4,275]. The delicate stability of TiB is related to the extremely low boron solubility in Ti, which is <0.0001 at.% in comparison to carbon (22 at.%) and nitrogen (1.8 at.%) [260]. The TECs of Ti and TiB are close to each other, which reduces the magnitude of residual stresses in the final composite [305]. Even extremely low concentrations of TiB can result in a large increase in strength, which is considerably higher than the effect of other reinforcements such as TiN and TiC [261]. Boron is a biocompatible element which makes it favorable to use TiB-reinforced composites in biomedical applications. Formation of *in situ* TiB phase in Ti-based matrix has also been attempted with the addition of TiB₂ particles [292]. The formation of TiB results from the *in situ* reaction between Ti matrix and TiB₂ particles. The TiB phase not only increases the biocompatibility but also increases the wear resistance [306]. As discussed, Ti IMCs compounds do not show good room temperature ductility and hence the development of TMCs is an efficient alternative for improving their mechanical behavior. Regrettably, no TMC feedstock powders are available commercially to date. Therefore, ball milling is the most common method opted for the mixing of initial powders. The production of TMCs is more challenging than that of the alloy itself, due to dissimilar mechanical and thermal behaviors of the reinforcement and matrix phases.

Attar et al. [51] used CP-Ti as matrix to fabricate Ti-based MMCs by TiB reinforcement. TiB reinforcement has become the most prevalent and highly explored reinforcement and optimizing the process parameters during the milling of Ti-TiB₂ initial powder mixtures and subsequent AM processing plays an important role for the formation of Ti-TiB composites. The SLM process inherently requires sphericity of the powders for efficient flowability, but commercial TiB₂ powders have an irregular polygon shape [289]. Therefore, both spherical CP-Ti and irregular-shaped TiB₂ powders are often ball milled together at optimized milling conditions so that the sphericity of CP-Ti is maintained after ball milling and a homogenous powder mixture can be achieved [51,282]. For an optimized rotation speed of 200 RPM and a milling duration of 2 h, Attar et al. [282] achieved homogenous and nearly spherical Ti-TiB₂ powder by ball milling. Unoptimized milling conditions result in non-uniformity of the powder or flattening of particles directly affecting the microstructure and resulting in defect formation upon

SLM [282]. Porosity was observed in optical micrographs of printed composites prepared from 4 h milled premixed powders, whereas a pore-free and dense microstructure was obtained after 2 h milling, as demonstrated in Fig. 19. The relative densities were calculated as 99.5% and 95.1%, respectively. The microstructure of the SLM composites revealed needle-shaped TiB particles uniformly distributed in an α -matrix. The orientation of the formed TiB phase shows a higher growth speed in [010]_{B27} direction than in the other directions, resulting in a needle/whisker-like shape.

In another study by Attar et al. [51], the milling duration was optimized for CP-Ti-TiB₂ powder mixing. There, the milling time was varied from 1 to 4 h at intervals of 1 h. One hour milling time resulted in non-uniform mixing, whereas increasing the milling time to 2 h created a rather uniformly distributed morphology, where TiB₂ particles were found to be strongly adhered to the spherical Ti particles. A further increase in milling time resulted in deformation and flattening of initially spherical-shaped particles. The effect of milling duration on the powder morphology is shown in Fig. 20. The energy density used for CP-Ti (120 J/mm³) resulted in high porosity. An increase in the laser power from 165 to 180 W at the same energy density improved the density but for higher power levels porosity reoccurred. Optimized conditions, which closely match with that used for Ti-TiC composites, led to a maximum densification of up to 99.5%. The final fabricated composite was found to have a total 8.35 vol.% TiB reinforcement phase as a result of *in-situ* reaction between Ti-5wt.% TiB₂ powder mixture after SLM [51].

Optimization of the energy density was also reported as important factor for achieving high densification through SLM. Attar et al. [51] and Gu et al. [52] reported that an energy density of 120 J/mm³ is optimum for CP-Ti parts. Addition of TiB₂ as reinforcement needed further optimization owing to its high melting temperature (~3225 °C). It was reported that an increase in energy density from 120 to 140 J/mm³ resulted in porosity and, hence, the laser power was increased from 165 to 180 W, while maintaining the same energy density. Moreover, the keyhole effect became less pronounced with increasing scanning speed [294]. A further increase in laser power up to 185 W resulted in a slight decrease in densification. The optimization of energy density, laser power, and scan speed allowed to achieve almost full densification for Ti-TiB composites [51].

The average micro-hardness of SLM Ti-TiB composites was found to be at least 1.5–2 times higher than that of the best commercially available Ti alloys, owing to the hardening effect from the TiB particles and grain refinement in the α -Ti matrix. The yield

Fig. 17. (a) Ti-TiC composite powder after 4 h of ball milling [286] and (b) SEM image of ball milled Ti-Si₃N₄ composite powder reported by Gu et al. [287]. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4834681045976 and 4833090452245 dated 20th May 2020 [286,287].

Fig. 18. SEM micrographs of SLM-produced TiC/Ti₅Si₃ composites at different energy densities (η) and scan speeds (v): (a-b) $\eta = 0.2$ kJ/m, $v = 0.4$ m/s; (c-d) $\eta = 0.267$ kJ/m, $v = 0.3$ m/s; (e-f) $\eta = 0.4$ kJ/m, $v = 0.2$ m/s; (g-h) $\eta = 0.8$ kJ/m, $v = 0.1$ m/s. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833090724900 dated 20th May 2020 [290].

Fig. 19. Ti-TiB₂ powder mixture milled for (a) 2 h and (b) 4 h; micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) images of SLM-processed Ti-TiB composite samples prepared from the Ti-TiB₂ powder mixture milled for (c) 2 h and (d) 4 h. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833090869390 dated 20th May 2020 [282]. SLM, selective laser melting.

Fig. 20. SEM micrographs of a Ti-TiB₂ powder mixture milled for (a) 1 h, (b) 2 h, (c) 3 h and (d) 4 h. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833090972496 dated 20th May 2020 [51].

Fig. 21. (a) and (b): morphology of TiB_2 reinforcements after milling for 4 h. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833091069924 dated 20th May 2020 [289].

Fig. 22. Schematics showing (a) powder mixture and fine TiB_2 particle distribution around large Ti particles before sintering, and (b) needle-shaped TiB phase formation by *in situ* reaction. Image inspired from a study by Sabahi Namini et al. [307].

strength and ultimate strength are higher than that of the CP-Ti and Ti-6Al-4V alloys [4,282]. The increase in yield strength delays the plastic deformation allowing the composite to be used for high-strength applications. However, the challenge remains to reduce the elastic modulus of the SLM Ti-TiB composites in order to be qualified for orthopedic applications. Further, the fabrication of TMCs is more complex than that of the base metal/alloy due to the high melting temperature and refractive nature of the reinforcements.

Cai et al. [289] reported ball milling of Ti-6Al-4V (20–70 μm) with TiB_2 ($D_{50} = 2.71 \mu m$) powders for 4 h. Uniformly distributed TiB_2 particles were found attached to the near spherical Ti-6Al-4V particles, as shown in Fig. 21. In addition, TiB reinforcements were embedded in the α -Ti matrix in the shape of needles with a length of 0.5–1 μm . The impact of different reinforcement contents (0, 1, 2, and 3 wt%) on the resulting properties of the composites has also been investigated in this study. Increasing the TiB_2 content resulted in agglomeration of the TiB phase. Higher reinforcement

Fig. 23. μ -computed tomography (CT) images of CP-Ti specimens manufactured by SLM; the porosity level in the samples was (a) 37%, (b) 17% and (c) 10%. Adapted with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd. under the license number 4833100256592 dated 20th May 2020 [4]. SLM, selective laser melting.

contents enhanced the hardness of the composite. A maximum hardness of 6.00 GPa and a minimum friction coefficient of ~0.35 were found for 3 wt% TiB₂.

Fig. 22 schematically depicts the *in situ* reaction of Ti and TiB₂ for the formation of TiB around larger CP-Ti particles. The following equation (9) is proposed for the formation of CP-Ti-TiB composites via the SLM process:

It is expected that complete TiB formation occurs due to the diffusion of boron from TiB₂ into the surrounding Ti matrix during melting and solidification [308]. The Gibbs free energy for equation (9) is negative and the concentration of B is less than the saturation limit (18–18.5 wt%) for TiB₂ formation from the phase diagram of Ti-B [81,308]. The TiB reinforcements in the composite are also found to be finer than those observed in cast composite microstructures [309]. This refined microstructure is attained due to extremely high heating and cooling rates (on the order of 10³–10⁸ K/s) during SLM, which impedes particle coalescence and grain growth. Enhancement in the yield and ultimate tensile strength are mainly the result of finer and uniformly distributed TiB reinforcements. The composite also shows much higher Vicker's hardness compared to the matrix material. A few other processing parameters such as the particles shape and size also play an important role in improving the density and mechanical properties. Ball milling was found to be the ideal process to achieve near spherical particles rather than gas atomization, which is more expensive [282].

Studies carried out to study the effect of the milling parameters on the production performance and quality of the Ti-TiB composites suggested the requirement to optimize the milling speed and duration to retain the nearly spherical shape, aiding in good flowability and high densification after SLM [4,51,282]. Nanoindentation was used in a recent study for non-destructive estimation of tribological and mechanical properties of SLM Ti-TiB composites [310], revealing higher hardness and better wear properties for composite specimens. The properties obtained from nanoindentation were consistent with the results acquired from conventional testing methods. A recent study on SLM of porous CP-Ti and Ti-TiB composites showed a decrease in Young's modulus with increasing average porosity (10%, 17%, and 37%) [4]. Examples of manufactured parts with clearly different porosity levels are shown in Fig. 23. Both CP-Ti and Ti-TiB with 37% porosity revealed similar strength and modulus values as human bone. In addition, *in vitro* corrosion test in Hank's solution showed a more extended passive region for Ti-TiB composites as compared with CP-Ti [311], indicating that the corrosion resistance increased due to the presence of intermediate TiB phase and unreacted TiB₂ grains in the composite. The refinement of Ti grains due to the presence of TiB also helps in improving the overall corrosion resistance of the composite. A few studies [292] reported on the fabrication of functionally graded Ti-TiB₂ composites by SLM, where the TiB₂ content was varied from 5 to 15 vol.% at intervals of 5 vol.%. Microhardness values for the 5 vol.%, 10 vol.% and 15 vol.% composites were measured as 450–500 Hv (4.413–4.904 GPa), 450–550 Hv (4.413–5.394 GPa) and 500–600 Hv (4.904–5.884 GPa), respectively. No change in phase formation was observed upon variation of the TiB₂ content.

TiAl-based composites, reinforced with TiB₂, were also reported for aerospace and high temperature applications [303]. For instance, 1–3 wt% TiB₂ was mixed in a Ti45Al2Cr5Nb (at.%) matrix during 4 h of milling [304]. This caused an increase in hardness from 9.96 to 10.57 GPa in the composites. An increase in hatch

speed caused a decrease in relative density by 6% and also resulted in grain refinement of the matrix [304].

4.1.3. Ti-CrB₂ composites by SLM

Cr is a β phase stabilizer [312]. It possesses high wear resistance, excellent corrosion resistance and good compatibility with the Ti matrix [312,313]. Hence, Ti-CrB₂ composites appeared to be of great interest. For manufacturing this composite by SLM, first 2 wt% CrB₂ were mixed with CP-Ti powder under optimized conditions [300]. Even at optimum energy density, partially melted and unmelted CrB₂ regions were observed along with molten CrB₂ areas attaining a maximum densification of 97.5%. *In situ* reaction between the Ti matrix and the CrB₂ particles resulted in TiB phase formation. A major influence was observed on the wear properties of such composites compared with pure CP-Ti. High hardness and lower wear rate were evident with the increase in TiB phase formation. The microhardness varied from 320 to 380 Hv (3.138–3.727 GPa) for different processing conditions. Applying higher energy densities resulted in higher TiB phase contents thus improving wear resistance and hardness. Moreover, the presence of Cr promoted the transition from β to α' martensite phase [300].

4.1.4. *In situ* Ti-(TiB + TiC) composites by SLM

Reinforcement of the Ti matrix with both TiB and TiC has been achieved by *in situ* reaction with boron carbide [268,293,314]. For this, 5 wt% B₄C powder were ball-milled with CP-Ti for 2 h by Xia et al. [293]. The authors discussed the effect of process parameters on the surface smoothness, instead of the densification of the SLMed composite. An increase in laser power from 125 to 200 W improved the surface finish. Phase analysis revealed the presence of α-Ti, β-Ti, TiB and TiC and residual B₄C particles in the SLM composite. A change in microstructural features was observed with the change in process parameters. The higher the laser power or energy density, the larger is the fraction of TiB and TiC formation in the composite. Zhang et al. [268] characterized the (TiB + TiC)/TC4 *in situ* Ti matrix composite by laser direct deposition. Composites were made by laser direct deposition of mixed TC4 and B₄C powders. The addition of 5 wt% B₄C resulted in a total 25 vol.% TiB + TiC reinforcement formation. In the fabricated composite, TiB phase was revealed to be needle-like and prismatic structure, whereas TiC formed in granular forms. Along with the *in situ* formed reinforcement phases, some unreacted B₄C were also found in the fabricated composite with a thin skull of reaction product around B₄C phase which deteriorated the surface bonding with matrix, leading to properties compromise [268].

4.1.5. *In situ* TiC- and TiN-reinforced Ti₅Si₃ matrix composites by SLM

Owing to its high temperature stability, Ti₅Si₃, instead of CP-Ti, forms an ideal matrix for Ti-based composites. Gu et al. [290] performed SLM of TiC-reinforced Ti₅Si₃ matrix composites. SiC powder was mixed in a weight proportion of 76.2:23.8 and embedded in a pure Ti matrix. Mechanical mixing was performed for 15 h. Different process parameters that were optimized to manufacture this composite by SLM are listed in Table 9. The linear energy density was varied from 0.2 to 0.8 kJ/m. SLM resulted in *in situ* Ti₅Si₃-TiC composite formation with the use of Ti and SiC powders. The chemical reaction between both initial powders occurred as a result of the applied energy density being above the melting temperature of SiC and the negative Gibbs free energy of the system. The chemical reaction of the powders during SLM can be described as:

Fig. 24. Schematic diagram of the microstructure evolution of SLM-processed Ti-nHA composites with different nHA additions, (Inspired from a study by Han et al. [172]). SLM, selective laser melting; HA, Hydroxyapatite.

The microstructure of the Ti_5Si_3 -TiC composites changed significantly with the change in energy density [290]. TiC changed from uniformly distributed slim dendrites to a network of refined dendrites when increasing the energy density up to 0.4 kJ/m. A further increase in energy density up to 0.8 kJ/m resulted in coarsened TiC dendrites. This is expected because of the instability of the solid-liquid interface due to perturbations. The effect of different process parameters such as scan speed and energy density on the microstructure, densification, and mechanical properties of the final composite has already been discussed in section 4.1.1 [290]. Later, Gu et al. [291] have also studied the effect of the addition of rare earth (RE) metals on the microstructure and mechanical properties of TiN-Ti₅Si₃ composites produced by SLM. Elemental Ti and Si₃N₄ powders were mixed along with RE-Si-Fe powder by milling for 10 h. The presence of Si₃N₄ caused *in situ* formation of TiN reinforcement phase in the Ti₅Si₃ matrix, and addition of 3 wt% of RE-Si-Fe resulted in smooth and rounded reinforcement surfaces. The addition of RE elements was also found to reduce the friction coefficient and the wear rate due to enhanced liquid-solid wettability [291].

4.1.6. Hydroxyapatite-reinforced Ti matrix composites

The osteointegration of Ti-based materials can be enhanced with the use of any bioactive ceramic. Hydroxyapatite (HA), a natural bone mineral, is one of the most widely used bioactive coatings on Ti-based materials [172].

The decomposition of HA occurs at around 800 °C [315]. Thus, their stability during high temperature processing is of concern. SLM of Ti-HA and Ti6Al7Nb-HA composites were carried out for their intended use in biomedical applications [172]. In a first step, 2 and 5 wt% HA were added and milled with pure Ti for 7 h for creating the starting powder for SLM. Fig. 24 illustrates the variation in microstructure with increasing HA content. While pure Ti exhibits long lath structures, addition of 2 wt% HA resulted in short acicular grains, which further transformed into quasi-continuous circular grains upon addition of 5 wt% HA.

Jackson et al. [316] added fine, amorphous boron powder to Ti-6Al-4V alloy powder by tumbling for 2 h. SLM of 0.5 wt% B-containing composites yielded samples with extremely brittle behavior, whereas 0.25 wt% B addition in the Ti-6Al-4V matrix yielded useful properties. Addition of 0.25 wt% B resulted in a refined morphology as compared to pure Ti-6Al-4V samples prepared with the same parameters, but no significant difference in density was observed. Up to 99.5% densification was achieved at optimized melting parameters. Deviation from the optimum energy density conditions resulted in porosity, occurring due to under-melting or gas entrapment. The hardness of the composite

was measured as 392.4 Hv (3.848 GPa), which was about 30 Hv (0.2942 GPa) higher than that of pure Ti-6Al-4V.

4.2. β -Ti matrix composites

As discussed in the previous sections, AM β -Ti alloys and parts are attractive because of their low modulus and the ease of fabrication of complex geometries, which are in high demand for biomedical, aviation and automobile applications. But other than the modulus, there usually are other properties which are required for specific applications which include higher strength, wear resistance, and hardness. Several articles report mixing with additional elements or reinforcements in different concentrations for improving the desired properties. One example is the addition of 10% Mo to Ti-6Al-4V and SLM of this mixture, resulting in a β -titanium matrix with Mo particles instead of an α' microstructure. In addition, Mo also reduced the β transus temperature from 1050 °C to ~900 °C [285].

Mantri et al. [317] performed LENS by adding 0.5 wt% boron to the Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ) β -Ti alloy. Microstructural analysis revealed an *in situ* formed acicular TiB reinforcement phase due to the boron addition. Moreover, lath-like α -Ti grains converted into more equiaxed shapes, whereas the pure TNZ alloy was found to have lath-like primary and secondary α -Ti precipitates dispersed in the β -Ti matrix. EBSD images of both the base alloy and B added TNZ samples are shown in Fig. 25. This observed microstructure refinement clearly enhanced the hardness and wear resistance of the composite. The average hardness increased from 325 to 450 Hv (3.187–4.413 GPa) and the wear rate decreased from $2.9 \pm 0.41 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ to $1.4 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$.

Majumder et al. [318,319] investigated the effect of boron addition in another β -Ti alloy, Ti-35Nb-5.7Ta-7.2Zr. Single stage and duplex stage heat treatments were performed to examine the effect on microstructure and mechanical properties. The *in situ* formation of TiB reinforcement phase was observed with the addition of 0.5 wt% B on sample fabrication by vacuum arc melting. In the pure alloy, the presence of ω and α phases was observed in the β -matrix, whereas addition of B resulted in the formation of TiB precipitates with no further refinement of the matrix. Addition of 0.5 wt% B resulted in about 3.2 vol.% TiB reinforcements with an acicular shape and a length in the range of 5–10 μm . B addition, however, did not seem to influence the yield strength and the fatigue behavior of Ti-35Nb-5.7Ta-7.2Zr.

Traxel and Bandyopadhyay [320] studied the effect of Zr and BN addition in a CP-Ti base system through reactive deposition as an AM method. Four different compositions were deposited including pure CP-Ti, (CP-Ti/20 wt%Zr), (CP-Ti/10 wt%BN) and (CP-Ti/18 wt%

Zr/10wt%BN) separately as 15 mm cross-sectional square patterns [320]. The purpose of selecting these four compositions was to evaluate the effect of reinforcements Zr and BN separately and to find a combined effect of both in titanium matrix. Process optimization for each composition was carried out to minimize the defect amount and achieve maximum densification. *In situ* Ti-boride and nitride reinforcement phases forms due to BN addition, whereas Zr provides solid solution strengthening of the Ti matrix composites, rendering them suitable for high temperature applications. BN also possesses a graphite-like structure and reduces the coefficient of friction between mating bodies [320]. This study reported the formation of TiN, TiB, and TiB₂ phases in the Ti-BN system. In case of the Ti-Zr-BN system, formation of ZrN, ZrB and ZrB₂ was found after fabrication. An increase in mechanical and tribological properties has been achieved for the LENS-produced composites as compared to pure CP-Ti. The composite reinforced with Zr alone showed 12% more hardness, 23% higher yield strength, and 11% less wear rate than the deposited titanium. The combination of Zr and BN addition

has been reported to have a drastic improvement in properties as it showed a 450% higher increase in hardness, that is, $\sim 1424 \pm 361$ Hv_{0.5/15} (13.97 ± 3.54 GPa) and 9 times less wear rate than the LENS deposited titanium [320].

Li et al. [321] studied the effect of reduced graphene oxide (RGO) addition on the microstructure and mechanical properties of Ti-43.5Al-6.5Nb-2Cr-0.5B composites. To achieve this task, they used a liquid deposition method for uniform attachment of RGO to the matrix and combined the process with SLM. The presence of RGO refined the microstructure and resulted in a higher compressive strength [321]. The variation in RGO content has shown a significant impact on the microstructural changes as base material was found to show 51.1%, 46.7% and 2.2% α_2 , γ and B₂ phases, respectively, which have changed to 55.6%, 41.5%, and 2.9% with the addition of 0.5% RGO. In the similar trend, α_2 continued to increase while γ and B₂ phase amounts decreased with a more uniform distribution of B₂ phase as RGO content increased. At maximum 2 wt% RGO content, γ phase reached up to 72.7%, whereas γ and B₂

Fig. 25. Electron back scattered diffraction images (EBSD)/ Inverse pole figure (IPF) maps of (a) TNZ and (b) TNZ-B. Discrete plots confirming the Burgers orientation relationship between α/β in (c) TNZ and (d) TNZ-B. XRD patterns of (e) TNZ and (f) TNZ-B. Adapted with permission from Springer under the license number 4833100942078 dated 20th May 2020 [317].

phase decreased to 23.1 and 4.2%, respectively. A superior compressive strength of 1546.88 MPa with 5.34% strain was attained for this novel TiAl/RGO composite after SLM [321].

Ma et al. [322] used elemental powders Ti, Al, and TiC for fabricating TiC/TiAl composites by SLM. Three different nucleation and growth modes were observed for TiC dendrite formation during solidification. These modes were classified on the basis of TiC melt formation, which was dependent on the laser energy density. Three modes of nucleation and growth belonged to the dissolution-precipitation of fully melt TiC fine particles, epitaxial growth along the margin of partly melted TiC particles and recrystallization growth based on the stress induced non-equilibrium melting [322]. The optimized laser energy density was reported as 189 J/mm³ for complete densification, and the specimens showed good high temperature oxidation resistance [322].

Recently, Zhou et al. [323] developed 5 wt% TiN-reinforced CP-Ti composites by SLM. Addition of TiN resulted in grain refinement of α' acicular martensite phase from 1.37 to 0.73 μm . The composites were found to consist of α' -Ti, δ -TiN and ϵ -Ti₂N phases. The study was focused on the corrosion behavior of the composite in HCl as compared with the base alloy. The composite showed enhanced corrosion resistance compared with the base alloy, where TiN was assumed to work as microcathode and passivated the composite surface. Passive layer was found to be mainly made up of TiO₂ on both the unreinforced and reinforced sample surfaces. With longer immersion times, uniform corrosion on the composite and larger pit formation on the base alloy surface were reported.

5. Outlook and future aspects

The abundant literature and studies on the development of selective laser melted Ti alloys and composites mostly aimed on the densification and mechanical behavior of the material. Strongly limited insights were obtained on their corrosion, high temperature oxidation and tribological behavior, other than for the few popular systems such as Ti-6Al-4V and CP-Ti. Despite the development of several alloys, single-phase CP-Ti still finds numerous applications in aviation and medicine, where moderate strength and high corrosion resistance are sought. On the other hand, for high loading conditions and variable modulus requirements, it is vital to modify the composition, phase formation, microstructure and design of the Ti alloys and composites. To meet such tailored needs, SLM has proved itself a powerful method to manipulate the structure and properties of Ti alloys and composites.

Based on the unique microstructural features and phase constitutions occurring in the non-equilibrium processing by SLM, several high performance materials specific to the intended applications have been developed. α and (α + β)-Ti alloys have been commonly specified for structural applications due to their outstanding mechanical properties, whereas β alloys have been proposed for biomedical applications mainly due to their low elastic modulus and high corrosion resistance under *in vitro* conditions. Unfortunately, however, most of these materials have not been tested *in vivo* and, hence, have not yet been implemented for commercial biomedical applications, which is foreseen as an area of intense future research on β alloys. Different groups have also tried to prepare porous (α + β)-Ti alloys for biomedical applications, especially for high load bearing conditions.

Several studies were focused solely on reducing the elastic modulus of high-strength (α + β)-Ti alloys so as to meet the requirements for biomedical applications. Addition of ceramic reinforcements via *in situ* or *ex situ* methods, as well as fabricating porous alloys and composites, were proposed in this context. Fine-

tuning of the elastic modulus was also performed on β -Ti alloys/composites by designing and fabricating triply periodic minimal surfaces or structures with well-defined porosity. However, lack of systematic *in vitro* and *in vivo* biological tests have refrained their commercial use so far.

This review also comprehensively discusses the influence of various powder and processing parameters on the structure-property correlations of Ti-based composites produced by SLM. For a composite, mixing and distribution of the reinforcement phase is a crucial factor for achieving the required microstructure, mechanical and tribological properties. The alloy powders that form the matrix of the composites are required to have a spherical shape in order to attain good flowability and high densification. The sphericity gets changed or damaged when milling is carried out under non-optimized conditions such as too high milling speed, or in the presence of hard grinding media for longer durations, or when the ratio of powder to grinding media is very high. The loss of sphericity of powder particles results in poor densification and consequently poor mechanical properties. Furthermore, it has also been observed in various studies that optimized milling results in a uniform attachment of reinforcement particles on the surface of spherical matrix particles. Such adhesion is highly beneficial as it leads to a uniform distribution of the reinforcement phase or any intermediate phase during the SLM process and in the ensuing composite. In view of this fact, the present review offers a compilation of various studies performed to optimize the powder processing during milling to obtain high densification upon SLM. Process modification by means of heat treatment, mechanical action, or addition of elements are well-known techniques for grain refinement in alloys and composites. Various efforts have been made for achieving grain refinement in Ti-based materials by using Sn, C, B, and so on for this purpose. Among all the additions considered, B has been identified as the most efficient grain refining element when added in small amounts. In large amounts, it forms *in situ* TiB reinforcements in the Ti matrix which are biocompatible and are mostly used for biological hard tissue replacements.

For further enhancing the tensile/compressive strength, as well as the fracture toughness of composites, the use of multiple reinforcements to produce hybrid composites is a popular and promising approach, which has not been much explored via the AM route. The use of two or more varieties of reinforcements at optimized parameters by SLM can help in achieving superior room-temperature and high-temperature strengths, and may also improve corrosion and wear resistance. So far, only the combination of TiC + TiB as reinforcement in a Ti matrix has been explored. For biological applications, the elastic modulus is as important a factor as the fracture toughness. However, when hard reinforcement particles such as TiB, TiC, SiC, and so on are added to the Ti matrix, the modulus cannot be reduced to the desired values, albeit an increase in strength and fracture toughness. In this case, porous structures with tailored elastic modulus are sought. Not much work has been carried out in developing porous composite structures for implant applications by using SLM. There are only very limited literature reports on balancing the elastic modulus and compressive strength of porous Ti-based composites produced by SLM. The present article provides a holistic review of the state-of-the-art SLM Ti alloys and composites mainly aimed at aviation and biomedical applications. AM of patient-specific porous Ti-based composites with high strength, wear resistance and perfect modulus match for biomedical applications, as well as composites with high specific strength and corrosion resistance for aviation and automobile applications constitute two most important future areas of research.

Data availability

Data collected from the previous literature has been properly given credit using reference numbers and images are reused after having permission from the corresponding publisher referred with license no.

Author contributions

KGP and JE conceived the idea. NS, PH, and RU wrote the article. GM, KGP, and JE reviewed and modified the article, and KGP supervised the whole process.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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